
D5.3 Report on training and education services for certified EPC issuers

Task 5.3 Research on training and education of certified EPC issuers

WP5 Towards people-centred EPCs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In various European countries, energy performance certification is conducted using diverse calculation methodologies, varying in levels of detail and tools, thereby necessitating differing levels of expertise among certifiers. This observation is supported by the analyses from the *crossCert* project, as detailed in other *crossCert* reports (Sayfekar and Jenkins, *D3.1 Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states, 2022* and *D3.2 Performance gap causation, 2023*).

Consequently, it is not unexpected to find varying educational and specialised training requirements for energy performance certificate (EPC) issuers¹ across different countries. The structure and content of specialised training programs also exhibit significant disparities. In some European countries, training for EPC issuers is mandatory and regulated at the national level, while in others, it is entirely voluntary or non-existent.

However, according to Article 25 of the EPBD (recast)², Member States must ensure that the energy performance certification of buildings is conducted independently by qualified or certified experts. Additionally, public information on training and qualified or certified experts must be regularly updated by the states. Article 28 of the Energy Efficiency Directive³ mandates Member States to encourage participation in certification, training, and education programs to ensure the necessary level of competences. By December 31, 2024, and at least every four years thereafter, Member States must assess whether the schemes guarantee the required level of competences.

The initial sections of this report provides an overview of the training schemes for EPC issuers in ten distinct European countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK). The data was gathered by *crossCert* partners in these countries through a dedicated questionnaire. The summarised information outlines the regulatory prerequisites for issuing building certificates, the criteria and guidelines for conducting specialized training for EPC issuers, and the curricula utilised in these training initiatives. A comparative analysis is conducted among the different countries, highlighting the most notable distinctions and potential good practices.

The most objective assessment of the discrepancies in each national training program for EPC issuers compared to the requirements of national building certification schemes can be conducted by national stakeholders. To achieve this, *crossCert* partners engaged in consultations at the national level through various means such as workshops, webinars, focus groups, interviews, and bilateral dialogues. Throughout these consultations, national stakeholders put forth a wide range of suggestions for enhancing national training programs for EPC issuers and, in some instances, for refining the training content. While many of these suggestions are specific to individual countries, several recommendations emerged that hold relevance across multiple nations. A common recommendation is to include information on recent changes in legislation related to Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) in training sessions. There is also a strong consensus on the need to provide training on new technologies and building indicators such as Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) and Sustainability Rating Index (SRI). Experts emphasize the importance of paying special attention to the practical side of training and highlighting specific issues, such as deep renovation. It is also recommended that training should be tailored to different professionals and include peer reviews among experienced assessors. Training should also cover Building Information Modelling

¹ EPC issuers, also referred to as EPC assessors, are professionals trained and certified to assess the energy performance of buildings following the established national EPC assessment protocol. They deliver the EPC assessment service to the clients and issue EPCs as part of the service, either as individuals or as contractors for a larger issuing authority.

² DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast) https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401275

³ DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023L1791>

(BIM) technologies and the digitization of the EPC process. Additionally, there is a strong emphasis on the need for EPC issuers to effectively communicate the content of EPCs to their clients. Notably, national stakeholders in countries without mandatory training for EPC issuers recognized the importance of training for EPC issuers. In Greece and Spain, national stakeholders believed that training should be made mandatory.

By examining practices in different countries related to EPC issuer training and considering proposals from various international research projects for the future of EPC training, we offer recommendations to those responsible for designing specialised national training programs, whether mandatory or voluntary. The overarching objective is to provide comprehensive training that empowers EPC issuers with the necessary knowledge and skills for their professional roles. Our analysis and resulting conclusions focus on the scope and structure of trainings, content, and certification processes, leading to the following key recommendations:

- Trainings should be customized to accommodate EPC issuers with diverse levels of qualification, featuring separate modules tailored to specific specialties. Complex building certifications require a multidisciplinary team of EPC issuers, whereas simpler buildings can be certified by individual EPC issuers.
- The training curriculum should emphasize the practical application of scientific knowledge in energy performance assessments and evaluations.
- Relevant topics, such as state-of-the-art technologies, deep energy renovation recommendations, and consumer information, should be covered in the training program.
- The general module should provide an overview of legislation, the assessment process, data sources, and other related aspects.
- Practical exercises should involve the use of national EPC software and tools, measurement exercises, and simulation of the building certification process.
- The certification process for complex buildings should involve an examination with two parts: knowledge assessment and presentation of certification work by interdisciplinary teams.
- EPC issuers should receive periodic follow-up training sessions, at least once every two years, which can be delivered online to reduce costs and time commitments. These sessions should be flexible and cater to professionals from various fields and levels of EPC issuers, covering topics relevant to their expertise.
- In cases of significant methodological changes, face-to-face courses with practical components may be necessary.
- The recurrent training content should be used to enhance and update the foundational training curriculum and materials.
- To streamline the process, it is recommended to establish a national online platform where training providers can announce upcoming sessions, EPC issuers can register and receive email notifications, and a centralized registry of completed trainings can be maintained.

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1 Introduction

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) mandates the issuance of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) to provide valuable insights into the energy efficiency of buildings. These certificates empower occupants and building owners to make informed decisions, while also supporting policymakers in formulating effective energy efficiency strategies. The new generation of EPCs should address the limitations of traditional certificates, offering enhanced accuracy and relevance. As EPCs may significantly influence the energy consumption behaviours and building practices, the quality and consistency of their issuance are of paramount importance.

High level of competence of the EPC assessors is a cornerstone for the quality of the EPCs. The *crossCert* project therefore aims to understand the training programs for EPC issuers across ten European countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK) and define the weaknesses and strengths of the existing training processes. This report presents the results of a comprehensive exploration of the training programs in these countries, with the objective of conducting a cross-country comparative analysis to uncover best practices and identify areas for improvement. By engaging stakeholders at the national level in interviews and collaborative workshops, we have tried to define the most appropriate recommendations for enhancing the training programs for EPC issuers. The final section of this report utilizes qualitative research outcomes to define potentials for improvement that can be applied across European countries. By standardizing high-quality training for EPC issuers, we envision a future where they can more effectively contribute to the EU's energy goals.

2 Methodology

The primary objective of this paper is to analyse the current training programs for EPC issuers in various European countries participating in the *crossCert* project. The aim is to identify weaknesses and gaps in these programs and define potential areas for improvement that can be applied across the EU. The initial step towards achieving this goal involves gathering the necessary information for conducting the analyses. A specialized questionnaire (Appendix 1) was developed and completed by project partners based on a survey of national regulatory frameworks, other relevant literature sources, and their own expertise in their respective countries.

The questionnaire is structured into three sections. The first section addresses national requirements for EPC issuers, the second section focuses on the organization and implementation of training programs for EPC issuers, and the third section pertains to the content of curricula in these training courses. The collected information was analysed separately within each of these three main topics, followed by a comparative analysis across different countries.

The results of the cross-country comparative analysis were documented in an initial version of the report. Project partners had the opportunity to present these findings to stakeholders in their countries through various formats such as focus groups, workshops, live sessions, or online platforms. This allowed for discussions on weaknesses and opportunities for improvement in national training programs for certificate issuers.

All identified weaknesses and recommendations were then compiled, and further cross-country analyses were conducted to identify common issues and recommendations highlighted by stakeholders across different countries. Additionally, a literature review was conducted to explore other recommendations related to training of EPC issuers in anticipation of potential changes in building certification with the next generation of EPC. These findings, along with the analysis of best practices from various countries, were used to formulate and recommend guidelines for optimal training program design to those responsible for developing training courses for EPC issuers.

3 General requirements for EPC issuers

In all *crossCert* countries under review there are regulatory requirements regarding the eligibility of EPCs issuers to provide this service. This section of the report describes the national specificities in terms of

the requirements for educational background, professional experience and for successfully completed specialized training. In all countries, these aspects are regulated in different types of normative documents – laws or supplementary regulations, directly aimed at energy efficiency or directed to other areas of the economy.

3.1 Education and professional experience requirements for EPC issuers

In most countries, the EPC issuers must meet certain educational requirements in order to acquire the permits to pursue this activity. Such requirements are regulated in six of the analysed European countries, with only the UK not having any specific requirements for educational background for EPC issuers.

In Bulgaria these requirements are specified in a narrow framework, so specialists from a very limited number of specialties can obtain a license to practice the job of an EPC issuer. These specialties are precisely listed in the regulation documents for persons who have graduated from university and for persons who have graduated from a technical high school. Nevertheless, the Bulgarian legislation allows professional qualification for EPC issuers awarded in a Member State of the European Union, or in another country – party to the Agreement on the European Economic Area, or in the Swiss Confederation, to be recognized, as the recognition of documents is carried out by the universities that organize the trainings.

Austrian regulations also list specific areas of educational background or professional practice, but they have a much wider scope, and a much larger range of individuals can meet these requirements. Austria is the only country where the possession of professional license in certain fields (see Table 1) is an alternative to the requirement to have a specific educational background in order to be eligible to issue an EPC.⁴

In the other countries analysed, the range of professionals who are eligible to carry out the activity is also wider in terms of requirements for educational background. In Slovenia and Poland an engineering university degree in a broad variety of specialties is required also including architecture and spatial planning. The educational degree required in Croatia and in Malta is not specified in so much detail, but a more general description of different specialties is proposed. In Croatia, like in Bulgaria a specialist graduate in professional study could be also eligible for EPC issuance, but undergraduates in university or professional study can also issue certificates but for simple technical systems only (see Section 3.3). In Greece only an engineering university degree is required without specifying any further restrictions. In Spain and in Denmark it is required from the EPC issuer to have a technical educational background with a university degree. The UK is the only country among those analysed in this report not having any requirements in terms of educational background for the EPC issuers.

All countries’ requirements for educational background for the EPC issuers are summarised in the following table.

Table 1- Countries’ requirements for background education of EPC issuers

Country	Educational background	OR Professional license
Austria	Civil engineers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Entitled are civil engineers with relevant authority, such as in particular: ● Architects, ● Civil engineers and engineering consultants for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Civil engineering ○ Industrial engineering - civil engineering ○ Technical physics ○ Process Engineering 	Tradesmen/Professionals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Master builder ● Electrical engineering ● Gas and sanitary engineering ● Heating technology ● Refrigeration and air-conditioning technology ● Ventilation technology ● Master woodworkers ● Engineering offices (consulting engineers), in particular in the

⁴ Different professions may have varying educational requirements based on the specific skills and knowledge needed to excel in those fields. These requirements can vary depending on the industry, job role, and level of expertise required for a particular profession and may be different from the educational background described in Table 1.

Country	Educational background	OR Professional license
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mechanical Engineering ○ Building services engineering 	<p>following specialist areas are qualified and authorised to issue energy performance certificates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Building physics ○ Electrical engineering ○ Building services engineering (installation, heating and air conditioning) ○ Interior design ○ Mechanical engineering ○ Technical physics ○ Environmental technology ○ Process engineering ● Chimney sweeper: limited field (see 3.3) ● Hafner (Someone who installs stoves): limited field (see 3.3)
Bulgaria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engineers (university degree) in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ HVAC ○ Thermal Power Engineering ○ Electrical Power Engineering and Electrical Equipment ○ Electricity supply and Electrical Equipment ○ Civil engineering ● Architects (university degree) ● Scientific degree awarded in the field of "Technical Sciences", professional field: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy ○ Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Automation ○ Architecture, Civil engineering and Geodesy ● Technical high school degree with professional profile: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Technician of energy facilities and installations ○ Technician-technologist for operation and maintenance of refrigeration and air conditioning equipment in the food industry ○ Electrician ○ Construction technician 	No
Croatia	<p>Completed graduate university study in architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering or electrical engineering</p> <p>or</p> <p>Completed specialist graduate professional study in architecture, construction, mechanical engineering or electrical engineering and at least 300 ECTS credits acquired during the study</p> <p>or</p>	No

Country	Educational background	OR Professional license
	Completed undergraduate university or undergraduate professional study in architecture, civil engineering, mechanical engineering or electrical engineering profession (for energy auditing of simple technical systems)	
Denmark	Building technical basic education at minimum level 4 or higher for a minimum of 3 years duration, according to the Danish qualification framework for lifelong learning	No
Greece	Degree in engineering	No
Malta	A degree in architecture or civil engineering, or built environment, or building services, or mechanical, or electrical engineering conferred by the University of Malta, or an equivalent degree	No
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional title of engineer or Master of engineering in: architecture, landscape architecture, fire engineering, or Graduation from a university degree program or postgraduate studies related to energy performance of buildings, performance of energy audits of buildings, energy-efficient construction and renewable energy sources, or Possession of building license (can be obtained after trade school) 	No
Slovenia	Level of education obtained under first cycle study programmes and classified at level 7 in the fields of study in accordance with the law governing the Slovenian Qualifications Framework, belonging to the narrow field of engineering or architecture, spatial planning and construction or wood, paper, plastics, glass and similar technology or physics.	No
Spain	Technicians who hold a university degree enabling them to draft any building project or to manage the direction and execution of building works (only college education is required)	No
UK	No	No

3.2 Requirements for EPC issuers to complete specialized professional training courses

Successful completion of a specialized training course for EPC issuers is not a prerequisite for obtaining permission to work as an EPC issuer in half of the countries surveyed. Only in five of these countries, this

is an additional mandatory condition along with the requirement to have a certain educational background. In Bulgaria, participation in such training course and successful passing of a follow-up exam is mandatory, and as a result, a certificate of professional qualification for energy auditing of buildings is issued by the training bodies. Participation in specialized training and passing an exam is also compulsory in Croatia, Denmark, Malta and Slovenia. In Croatia it is required that the energy consultants participate in a refresher training course every two years, and in Denmark every three years to continue to be eligible to issue EPCs.

In the UK the requirements to the EPC issuers are focused more on their participation in training courses rather than background education. The trainings vary with building type as it will be presented in Section 3.3. Participation in continuing training is required for all EPC issuers – an annual training of 10 hours per year. An assessment/exam must be passed to receive this accreditation, providing a “London City and Guilds” qualification that is required for conducting any EPC.

There are no specific training requirements for EPC issuers in Austria, Greece, Spain and Poland. It is not mandatory to have completed specialised training course in order to work as an EPC issuer. However, in Austria there are voluntary training courses offered by calculation-tool-manufacturer (e.g. ArchiPHYSIK), energy agencies (e.g. Energy and Environment Agency of the Province of Lower Austria) or Public institutions (Economic Development Institute WIFI) that can be attended to specialise or deepen in certain areas.

Table 2- Countries’ requirements for completion of specialized training courses for EPC issuers

Country	Participation in specialized trainings for EPC issuer
UK	Mandatory participation in training courses varying for different building types.
Bulgaria Croatia Denmark Malta Slovenia	Mandatory participation and passing of exam.
Austria	Not mandatory, but voluntary trainings are organised
Greece Poland Spain	Not mandatory

3.3 Tired licenses based on different competence requirements

Some crossCert partner countries have different requirements regarding the competence of the EPC issuers depending on the different building types and/or the complexity of the building they are certified to assess.

In the UK, the training programmes for EPC issuers are tailored according to the required level of competencies for the EPC issuers. “Level 3” competence is for residential energy assessments (using steady-state models) and it is just based on a specific 1-2 week training programme without any requirement of previous qualifications. “Level 4” is for non-residential energy assessments (using steady-state models) and is similar but trained on different software. “Level 5” is for non-residential energy assessments (using dynamic models) and requires more training for the EPC issuers to be able to use accredited dynamic modelling to generate the EPC.

In Bulgaria, there are two levels of competence for the EPC issuers. “Level 1” consultants have competence to carry out energy auditing and certification of all building categories. These consultants could be legal

persons only employing at least one of the specialists from each profile listed in Table 2 above (min three staff members). "Level 2" consultants have competence to carry out energy auditing and certification only for residential and mixed-purpose buildings with low number of floors (up to 10 m in height) and villas. They can be individuals who have a specified set of technical means and the education degree and experience corresponding to one of the three profiles described in Table 2.

The levels of competence of the EPC issuers in Croatia are determined according to the complexity of the building and the technical systems. Buildings defined with simple technical systems have a gross building area of less than or equal to 600 m² with a maximum of three independent usable units and with:

- individual devices for the preparation of domestic hot water and not equipped with heating, cooling, ventilation systems;
- a central heat source for heating and domestic hot water preparation with a rated boiler power of up to 30 kW, without special heat recovery systems;
- local heat sources for heating and domestic hot water preparation with a single rated boiler power of up to 30 kW, without special heat recovery systems;
- solar collectors for the preparation of domestic hot water up to 7 m² of absorber surface; air system heat pump – air heat source with a rated output of up to 12 kW;
- individual refrigeration units;
- local decentralised ventilation systems with or without heat recovery, and without additional air treatment.

Specific parts of a building having a separate heating meter, gas central heating, connection to a common boiler room or connection to district heating are defined also with simple technical systems. All buildings that do not meet the criteria listed above are considered as buildings with complex technical systems.

The Energy Consultants in Denmark who can perform energy certification of buildings are divided in two categories. Those falling in the first category are eligible for certification of single-family houses only and the rest who are in the second category can certify all other types of more complex buildings.

In Austria, there are two types of professionals who have limited eligibility to issue an EPC. Chimney sweepers are only eligible for issuing EPCs for existing residential buildings, excluding new buildings and alterations to structures requiring a building permit, and Hafner (installers of heating stoves) are eligible for issuing EPCs for detached and semi-detached houses only. For all other building types with more complex energy and heating systems, the level of competence is required to be higher, and the only remaining professionals listed in Table 2 above are eligible to issue an EPC.

In Greece three categories of EPC issuers exist, each of them eligible to certify buildings with different total area. Class A EPC issuers may certify only buildings up to 250 sqm, class B EPC issuers – up to 1000 sqm and Class C EPS issuers – bigger buildings.

Four of the crossCert partner countries – Malta, Poland, Slovenia and Spain do not have any requirements related to different levels of competence of the EPC issuers for different building types.

Table 3- Countries' required levels of competences for different building types

Country	Tired licenses based on different competence requirements
UK	"Level 1" – assessing of simple residential buildings with low complexity "Level 2" – assessing of residential buildings with additional features such as multiple heating systems, air conditioning units, renewable energy technologies "Level 3" – assessing more complex residential buildings, including those with multiple heating systems or renewable energy technologies. "Level 4" – non-residential energy assessments (using steady-state models) "Level 5" – non-residential energy assessments (using dynamic models)

Country	Tired licenses based on different competence requirements
Bulgaria	<p>"Level 1" – energy auditing and certification of all building categories. Legal persons.</p> <p>"Level 2" – energy auditing and certification only for residential and mixed-purpose buildings with low number of floors (up to 10 m in height) and villas.</p>
Croatia	<p>Energy certification and energy auditing for buildings with a simple technical system,</p> <p>Energy certification of buildings with a complex technical system,</p> <p>Energy auditing of buildings with a complex technical system – in the part relating to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the building structures, - mechanical technical system, - electrical technical system, - automatic regulation and control systems, <p>Regular inspection of the heating and cooling systems or air conditioning systems in buildings.</p>
Denmark	<p>Energy Consultant 1 – certification of single-family houses</p> <p>Energy Consultant 2 – certification of multi-family houses and commercial buildings</p>
Austria	<p>Professionals (except two trades) listed in Table 2 are allowed to issue EPCs.</p> <p>There are to restrictions:</p> <p>Chimney sweepers are allowed to issue EPCs for existing residential buildings apart from new buildings and changes to buildings requiring a building permit.</p> <p>Hafner (someone who installs stoves) are allowed to issue EPCs for detached and semi-detached houses.</p>
Greece	<p>Class A EPC issuers – certification of buildings (or building units) up to 250 sqm</p> <p>Class B EPC issuers – certification of buildings (or building units) more than 250 and up to 1000 sqm</p> <p>Class C EPC issuers – certification of buildings (or building units) more than 1000 sqm</p>
Malta Poland Slovenia Spain	No division by levels of EPC assessment competence

3.4 Professional experience requirements for the EPC issuers

This section summarizes the differences in the requirements in the different countries regarding the professional experience as a condition to become an EPC issuer. In Bulgaria, Croatia and Slovenia having professional experience is an additional condition to the educational background requirement. In Slovenia the professional experience must be in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources in buildings. In Bulgaria the professional experience field is not specified but a different number of years of professional experience are required for different educational diploma degrees. Different periods of professional experience are required in Croatia for eligibility to issue EPCs for buildings with simple technical systems and for buildings with complex technical systems (see Section 3.3).

In Greece, the professional experience is not an eligibility condition to become an EPC issuer, but it is used to determine the different levels of EPC issuers (see Section 3.3). All of them start at Class A and move to a higher level in dependence of the number of EPCs issued (see Table 4). As already described in section

3.1. in Austria not the professional experience, but the availability of license in certain fields (see Table 1) is an eligibility condition for a person to become an EPC issuer.

Table 4- Professional experience requirements for EPC issuers

Country	Requirements for professional experience for EPC issuer
Austria	Professional licence in certain fields is required by the EPC issuers (see Table 1)
Bulgaria	Not less than 6 years for persons with high school diploma degree, not less than 3 years for persons with "Bachelor" degree and not less than 2 years for persons with "Master" degree and for persons with scientific degree.
Croatia	At least 5 years of work experience in the profession for complex technical system and at least 10 years of professional experience (but combined with lower education degree and specific training completion requirements) for simple technical system
Slovenia	Two years of relevant professional experience in the professional field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources in buildings
Greece	Professional experience requirements are applied to determine different levels of EPC issuers: Class A EPC issuers – starting level for all EPC issuers Class B EPC issuers – more than 30 EPCs, 6 of which are for tertiary sector buildings Class C EPC issuers – more than 10 class B EPCs
Denmark Malta Poland Spain UK	None

4 National specifics regarding specialized trainings for EPC issuers

The conditions under which trainings for EPC issuers are organised varies considerably from one European country to another. In some countries, such as Bulgaria, Slovenia and Denmark, they are regulated by national legislation and are mandatory for all interested parties, in other countries such as Austria, Greece, UK, they are mainly held under conditions specified by authorised institutions or by course organisers, and in third countries such as Spain and Poland, such courses are not organized at all. This section provides an overview of the main aspects related to the implementation of trainings in different countries.

4.1 Institutions providing trainings for the EPC issuers

The countries where the specialised trainings courses for EPC issuers are mandatory apply different approaches when authorising training providers to perform training courses for EPC issuers. In Bulgaria the organizations that have the right to organise training courses for EPC issuers are defined in the Energy Efficiency Law. Such are universities educating in the field of "Technical Sciences", professional fields "Energy", "Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Automation" and "Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy", accredited under the Higher Education Act. Practically, there are seven universities in the county who can provide the trainings.

In Slovenia, the Law on Efficient Use of Energy prescribes the obligations related to the training of experts, the conditions for obtaining licences for producers and authorisations for EPC issuers. At present, two institutes have been selected by the State through a public tender process to serve as EPC training providers – Gradbeni institut ZRMK, d.o.o. (GI ZRMK), and Zbornica za arhitekturo in prostor Slovenije

(ZAPS). Other specialised trainings may be organised by various providers, however, the participation is voluntary.

The Ministry of physical planning in Croatia approves the legal entities that can provide trainings for EPC issuers (Program holders). The approvals have time limits of 5 years and can be reissued for the same period when expired. Currently, there are eight regionally distributed institutions (faculties and professional organisations) that were granted authorisation for carrying out the training programme.

In Denmark, as of 15th of October 2015, training of energy consultants must be carried out at a state-funded educational institution. The programme is offered at Copenhagen Business Academy (KEA), Business Academy Dania, Business Academy Midt VEST, University College Northern Jutland, and UCL Business Academy.

All EPC trainings in Malta (residential and non-residential) are conducted by the Building and Construction Authority. The Building and Construction Authority (BCA) was set up through the Building and Construction Act of 2021 and is responsible for safeguarding third parties and safe working practices by ensuring that core aspects of a building's life cycle are developed effectively and follow up-to-date regulations applied in a controlled environment. Prior to the setting up of the BCA, EPC trainings were under the responsibility of the Building Regulations Office (BRO).

In countries where it is not specifically regulated on national level who can provide trainings for EPC issuers, there is a wide variety of organisations offering such trainings. In Austria, the commercial authorisation of the EPC issuers is regulated by the Austrian Federal Economic Chamber (WKÖ) but it is not automatically linked to the completion of any of the courses offered. A long list of institutions are allowed to train EPC issuers: Lower Austrian Energy and Environment Agency (eNu); Energy Agency Styria; Economic Development Institute WIFI; Universities of Applied Sciences; Building Academy of the Federal States; Energy Institute Vorarlberg; Energy Agency Tyrol; Energieberatung Salzburg; Office of the Carinthian Provincial Government; Burgenland Eco-energy Fund; and City of Vienna.

In UK, three awarding bodies exist: Awarding body for the Built Environment (ABBE), City and Guilds, and National Association of Estate Agents. Those are institutions who have the role to develop qualifications and assessments which are valid and reliable and are responsive to customer needs and approve training providers to deliver their qualifications. Particularly, these awarding bodies develop qualification and assessment schemes for EPC issuers. The training schemes are run by a large number of organisations approved by the awarding bodies.

The most liberal is the training system in Greece, where specialized training on EPCs is organised by a number of private or non-governmental establishments offering vocational education.

Table 5- Institutions providing trainings for EPC issuers in European countries

Country	Institutions providing training of EPC issuers	EPC training providers regulated by specific act
Bulgaria	Universities educating in the field of "Technical Sciences", professional fields "Energy", "Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Automation" and "Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy", accredited under the Higher Education Act (Technical University of Sofia; Technical University of Varna; Technical University of Gabrovo; Technical University of Ruse; University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy in Sofia; Thracian University – Faculty „Technics and Technology” in Yambol; Food Technologies University in Plovdiv.)	Yes - Energy Efficiency Law
Croatia	Legal entities that have the consent of the Ministry of physical planning (program holders) for a period of five years, and approval may be reissued for the same period. Currently, there	Yes

Country	Institutions providing training of EPC issuers	EPC training providers regulated by specific act
	are eight regionally distributed institutions (faculties and professional organisations) that were granted authorisation for carrying out the training programme.	
Denmark	State-funded educational institutions (Copenhagen Business Academy (KEA), Business Academy Dania, Business Academy Midt VEST, University College Northern Jutland, and UCL Business Academy)	Yes
Malta	Building and Construction Authority (BCA) set up through the Building and Construction Act of 2021.	Yes
Slovenia	Gradbeni institut ZRMK, d.o.o. (GI ZRMK), and Zbornica za arhitekturo in prostor Slovenije (ZAPS)	Yes – Rules on the efficient use of energy in buildings
Austria	Lower Austrian Energy and Environment Agency (eNu); Energy Agency Styria; Economic Development Institute WIFI; Universities of Applied Sciences; Building Academy of the Federal States; Energy Institute Vorarlberg; Energy Agency Tyrol; Energieberatung Salzburg; Office of the Carinthian Provincial Government; Burgenland Eco-energy Fund; and City of Vienna	No
UK	Large number of organisations approved by the Awarding bodies.	No
Greece	Private or non-governmental establishments offering vocational education	No
Poland Spain	No trainings for EPC issuers	No

4.2 Participation in trainings for EPC issuers and examination

Specific training conditions like frequency of organisation of trainings for EPC issuers; frequency of participation in training by the EPC issuers; existence of restrictions for participations in trainings; examination of training participants, vary a lot among the European countries where these training are organised. A review of these conditions by countries is presented further on in this section.

In Bulgaria, there is no rule regarding the frequency of conduction of trainings, but the frequency of conduction exams for acquiring of professional qualification for energy auditing of buildings (issuing EPCs) is regulated. The training providers for EPC issuers are obliged to hold examinations at least once a year. The EPC issuers need to participate in training only once, to pass an exam and to get a professional qualification certificate. Periodic trainings are not required. Certificates can be issued only to consultants who have the required background education as described in Section 3.1. The exam test is unified for all universities. A Methodological Council, which includes habilitated lecturers of all universities conducting examinations, prepares the test. The examination is conducted by an examination committee, which is appointed by the rector of the respective university. The members of the examination committee shall include habilitated lecturers from the university conducting the examination, at least two habilitated lecturers from other universities where examinations are held; the Chairman of the Methodological

Council, one expert from the specialized administration of the Ministry of Energy and one expert from the specialized administration of the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works.

In Slovenia, both training providers for EPC issuers organise at least three courses per year. The EPC issuers are obliged to attend in specialised training every 5 years after they obtain a license for EPC issuer. There are no limitations regarding the participation in EPC training, however the participants are informed in advance that a licence for EPC issuer will be awarded only to the experts fulfilling the requirements regarding the education and expertise as described in Section 3.1. A written and oral exam is a condition for successfully completed training. The oral exam is led by a committee of 3 senior professionals and covers the analysis of 2 EPCs prepared by the candidate and technical questions regarding building energy performance and recommended measures. The exams are conducted by the two institutions organising the trainings. EPC issuers must pass the exam only once. Participation in periodical trainings is mandatory for licenced EPC assessors who wish to extend their licence, however, the trainings do not include examination.

Every training provider (Program holder) in Croatia is required to organize a course at least once a year and may also offer online training sessions on an ongoing basis. EPC issuer candidates are obligated to participate in an initial training course and pass a comprehensive exam that includes both theoretical and practical components, namely conducting an energy audit and preparing an EPC. Only authorized physical persons employed by entities that perform energy auditing, building certification, or inspection of heating, cooling, and air-conditioning systems are eligible to participate in these training courses. Moreover, all EPC issuers are required to attend a refresher training program every two years to stay up-to-date with the latest regulations and technologies.

In Denmark, trainings of EPC issuers are organised annually in accordance with demand. The Energy Consultants have to follow a compulsory update training every 3 years. There are no restrictions regarding the right to participate in training, but it is regulated that a certificate of qualification is issued only to a person with education in the field and specialty corresponding to the requirements described in Section 3.1. The training is concluded with an exam documenting the theoretical and practical learning objectives. The practical part will document the learning in relation to a visual inspection of a real building. The exams are conducted by the eligible training institutions above following the criteria given by Declaration on Energy Labelling of Buildings and its annexes (18.11.2020). In addition to exams, energy consultants must participate in compulsory courses and meetings in accordance with the Danish Energy Agency's provision.

Although in Malta the training courses are mandatory for EPC issuer candidates there is no regulation about the frequency of organisation and participation in the courses. Only professionals with an educational background required for EPC issuers (see 3.1) can participate in the trainings. The organiser of trainings – BCA is responsible for examination of the participants in the courses.

In the countries where a specific national regulation on trainings for EPC issuers does not exist, like in Austria or in Greece, there are no fixed rules about the frequency of conduction of trainings, frequency of participation in trainings or about specific prerequisites for the participation. However, in Austria, some courses may require some prior knowledge or experience in certain areas. It is also possible that some training courses are only open to people with certain qualifications or certifications. If there are exams, they are usually carried out by the offering education body or the Working Group on Energy Advisor Training (ARGE-EBA). Differently from the countries with regulated trainings for EPC issuers, in Austria, it is possible to take an exam without attending a training course if you have acquired the necessary knowledge and skills elsewhere (e.g. at the University of applied Science). In Greece, it is up to the organiser to decide if there will be exams for the participants in the trainings. No requirements regarding the frequency of participation in training for EPC issuers exist in UK, except the regular annual CPD training, mentioned in Section 3. Many of the courses are provided online and usually a series of onsite assessments are carried out to demonstrate competence after a formal training course. EPC assessors wishing to upgrade their certification level from Level 3 to Level 4 or 5 need to present an assessment portfolio, attend further training and pass the corresponding examination.

Table 6- Specific conditions of trainings for EPC issuers in European countries

Country	Frequency of organisation of trainings for EPC issuers	Frequency of participation of trainings for EPC issuers	Restriction for participation in trainings for EPC issuers	Examination of participants in trainings for EPC issuers
Bulgaria	At least once per year by every provider	Only participation in initial training is obligatory. No obligation for participation in periodic trainings.	Only for experts with educational background in accordance with the conditions in Table 1	Written test and oral defence of conducted energy audit of a building.
Croatia	At least once per year by every provider	Participation in initial training and at least once a two-year period attending art training program for authorised persons to be updated with the new regulations and technologies The programme holders may also implement online training - constantly available regardless of the number of registered participants	Only for authorized physical persons and appointed and other employed persons, who conduct energy certification, energy audit of the building and regular inspection of heating systems and cooling systems or air conditioning in the building, in authorized legal entities.	Knowledge test in written form and practical part including development of an energy audit report and EPC.
Denmark	Annually in accordance with demand	Every 3 years	No but only experts with educational background in accordance with the conditions in Table 1 can receive certificate	Yes - the exam documents the theoretical and practical learning achievements of the participants.
Malta	No regulation	No regulation	Only professionals with an educational background required for EPC issuers (see 3.1)	Yes - organised by the BCA and usually held a week after the training
Slovenia	At least three per year by every provider	Every 5 years	No but only experts with educational background in accordance with the conditions in Table 1 can receive certificate	Written test and oral exam presenting analyses of 2 EPCs.
Austria	No regulation	No regulations	No	Up to the training providers

Country	Frequency of organisation of trainings for EPC issuers	Frequency of participation of trainings for EPC issuers	Restriction for participation in trainings for EPC issuers	Examination of participants in trainings for EPC issuers
UK	No regulation	No regulations except for the annual participation in CPD	No	Series of onsite assessments carried out to demonstrate competence after formal training course. For Level 3 assessors to become accredited for Level 4 and 5 assessments exams and a training and an assessment portfolio are rewired
Greece	No regulation	No regulations	No	Up to the training providers
Poland Spain	No trainings for EPC issuers	-	-	-

4.3 Official registration of participants in EPC training

In countries where training for EPC assessors is regulated, there is no mandatory requirement for training providers to maintain an official registry of professionals who have completed the training. However, all countries have established official registries of licensed EPC issuers that meet the requirements outlined in Section 3 of this report. These registries are maintained by national or regional authorities or professional organizations.

5 Content of the specialized training for EPC issuers

5.1 Scope of the trainings for EPC issuers

In the analysed countries where training for EPC issuers is mandatory under national law, the scope and content of the courses are also regulated, by means of the following acts:

- Bulgaria – *Ordinance E-RD-04-1 from 3.01.2018 for the circumstances subject to entry in the registers under the Energy Efficiency Act, the entry and receipt of information from these registers, the terms and conditions for acquiring qualification by energy efficiency consultants* (https://www.seea.government.bg/documents/NAREDBA_ERD041_ot_3012018_g_za_obstoqtel_stvata_podlejasi_na_vpisvane_v_registrite_po_Zakona_za_energ.pdf);
- Croatia – *Ordinance on persons authorised to issue energy performance certifications of buildings, energy audits of buildings and regular controls of heating and cooling or AC systems of buildings* (OG 73/2015, 133/2015, 60/2020, 78/2021) ([Pravilnik o osobama ovlaštenim za energetsko certificiranje, energetski pregled zgrade i redoviti pregled sustava grijanja i sustava hlađenja ili klimatizacije u zgradi \(nn.hr\)](#) Annex: [NN - 2015 - 073 - 01.07.2015.indd](#))
- Denmark – *Declaration on Energy Labelling of Buildings* (18.11.2020) and its Annex: “Additional requirements for companies carrying out energy labelling” ([Bekendtgørelse om energimærkning af bygninger \(retsinformation.dk\)](#))
- Slovenia – *Regulation on training, licences and register of licences of independent experts for the production of energy performance certificates* (Official Journal of the Republic of Slovenia, No 30/18 and 158/20 – ZURE (<https://pisrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAV13413>))

In Bulgaria the scope of the training program includes theoretical part with lectures and practical part. The length of the training is differentiated for Level 1 and Level 2 consultants. The training programs includes 75 hours of lectures and 40 hours of practical work. For Level 2 consultants the training program is shorter and includes 50 hours of lectures and 30 hours of practical work.

Croatian training program consists of Module 1 (for simple technical system) and Module 2 (for complex technical system). Module 1 includes 40 hours of lectures. Module 2 has a different agenda and number of hours for professionals of different specialities: 24 hours for architects and civil engineers; 30 hours for mechanical engineers; and 16 hours for electrical engineers. The training programme set out in Module 2 may only be attended by persons who have successfully completed the training programme set out in Module 1.

In Denmark the training program for EPC issuers is divided in four modules: Theoretical Basic Module; Basic module with direction for Energy Consultant 1 (Single family houses); Module for Energy Consultant 2 (Multifamily buildings and Commercial buildings); and Refresher course for energy consultants. The length of the training for Energy Consultant 1 is 7 days including theoretical and practical parts and exam. The length of the training for Energy Consultant 2 is 3 days of lectures of 7 lessons and an exam. The Refresher course has a scope of 1-day lectures of 7 lessons and one practical case.

In Slovenia the training length is 4 days and includes 29 hours of lectures specified in the regulation plus a practical part.

Malta does not have a regulation about the scope and content of the training courses but the training provider – BCA is responsible for setting up the curriculum.

In the other countries where trainings for EPC issuers are available the scope of the training program is not regulated and varies for different training providers. For example, the training course of ARGE-EBA (a voluntary course for energy advisors/to become an energy advisor and be able to issue an EPC) in Austria offers a basic program and an advance program. The basic training comprises 50 teaching units, and the advanced course, where the contents of the basic training course are deepened comprises 120 teaching units. In UK, the training courses are usually described as 1-2 week programme, with additional activities (such as onsite assessments which are submitted for checking) typically being a few extra weeks in terms of the overall process. For example, the Elmhurst's ABBE training course for Domestic Energy Assessors is 5 day long including 3 days classroom training, as well as 2 days of on-site visits where assessors are able to carry out actual EPC Surveys.

5.2 General topics included in the lectures at the trainings for EPC issuers

Bulgaria and Slovenia are the only two analysed countries where the lectures included in the training program for EPC issuers are specified in the national regulations. In Bulgaria, even more, the number of hours for each lecture are also regulated.

In Bulgaria, the training program for Level 1 consultants includes 71 hours of lectures dedicated to Energy auditing and building certification. General topics of the lectures include: EU and national legislation on energy auditing of building and energy performance certification; building typologies; building envelope elements; heat transfer; thermal bridges; measurements; energy performance calculation; energy modelling; building subsystems consuming energy; renewable energy installations; feasibility evaluation of energy saving measures; energy performance certificates; etc. The training program for Level 2 consultants includes 46 hours of lectures dedicated to Energy auditing and building certification with the same general topics but with some lectures are skipped and some have shortened content.

In Slovenia the length of lectures is not prescribed, however the timing is allocated adequately among the topics. The training programme is divided in 5 general categories – Energy performance certificate regulations; Determination of the energy performance of buildings; Measures to increase energy efficiency; Process for carrying out a building survey for the purpose of drawing up an energy performance certificate; and Practical implementation of the production and issue of an energy performance certificate. The full agenda includes 24 lectures.

In Croatia, the training program for Module 1 (for simple technical systems) includes lectures on regulations in the field of energy efficiency, energy audits and energy certification of buildings, as well as on basics of energy and buildings physics, construction of buildings, heating systems, lighting systems and on implementation of energy audit of the building and technical heating system. It also includes practical classes on energy auditing, EPC completion and on preparation of report on inspection of simple technical systems. Module 2 training program has different content for different professionals but always includes lectures on energy efficiency regulations and practical classes on conduction of energy audits of buildings with a complex technical system, preparing reports and recommendations with different length and details. The other lectures are specific for the respective speciality. Every training course finishes with an exam.

In Denmark, the content of the training program for EPC issuers is also regulated but in a different way. The regulations do not prescribe the topics and the list of the lectures but describe the minimum knowledge and skills that have to be obtained by any participant in each of the training modules.

Full content of the training programs for EPC issuers in Bulgaria, Slovenia and all requirements to the training programs in Croatia and Denmark are presented in Annex 2.

In other countries, where the training program content is not regulated at the national level the content varies for each training provider. For example, the course content of ARGE-EBA in Austria includes five general topics: Energy (situation, policy, useful energy, final energy, primary energy, indoor climate, emission factors, use of renewable and fossil energy sources, etc.); Building envelope (U-value, energy performance indicators, calculation procedure of the energy certificate, OIB guideline, construction and insulation materials, heating load, heating demand, economic efficiency, etc.); Heat generation and heat output (comfort, low and high temperature heat output systems, heat distribution, control, boilers, water heating and hot water distribution); Renewable energies (solar thermal, photovoltaics, biomass, heat pumps); and Electricity (household appliances, lighting, green electricity, energy label, rebound effect). Also in Austria, the calculation software companies offer some specialised trainings including update of the requirements for energy efficient buildings and requirements for EPCs and their calculation procedure or also trainings about different elements of EPC calculation, e.g. correct geometry calculation, summer overheating, upload and access to the EPC databases etc. The newest training course „Certified EPC issuer“ intended for people who are authorized to issue an EPC, is developed by Quality Austria in cooperation with ARGE-STIBA HOLDING Academy, the Austrian Building Academies (lecturers from the regional building guilds, industry and business) and klimaaktiv (lecturers from the Federal Ministry) (see Appendix 2). It continues 5 days and contains 4 modules including lectures on fundamentals for the calculation of energy performance; building physics; effects of various measures on energy performance indicators; relevant laws and standards; and know-how for submission and consultation; and exam preparation, a certification exam and knowledge check for external exam candidates, as well.

The Elmhurst's ABBE 5-day training course for Domestic Energy Assessors for domestic energy assessors in UK includes 10 training modules about ABBE Level 3 Qualification and requirements, the EPC Requirement and Exemptions; The RDSAP Software and background; Property types and building regulations, ages and construction; measurements, building envelope, building systems, etc.

5.3 Practical part in the trainings for EPC issuers

A practical part is included in the training agenda in all crossCert countries where the training program for EPC issuers is regulated. In Bulgaria, each participant in the trainings must develop an energy audit and prepare a complete set of documentation required by Law – an energy audit report, an energy audit summary, and a building EPC for one building within 40 training hours for a Level 1 consultant and 30 hours for a Level 2 consultant. A public service building with heating and cooling systems should be audited by Level 1 consultants, and a residential or mixed-purpose building with a low number of floors (up to 10 meters in height) by Level 2 consultants. For Level 2 consultants a residential or mixed-purpose building with a low number of floors (up to 10 m in height) should be audited and a complete set of documentation should be prepared – an energy audit report, an energy audit summary, and a building energy performance certificate.

In Croatia, practical classes of Module 1 and Module 2 are conducted on a concrete example of a building with a simple technical system or respectively with a complex technical system using a computer tool approved by the Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets. The practical part of the knowledge test consists of energy auditing of the building, i.e. the technical system of the building (heating system and cooling or air conditioning system) and EPC preparation. It is considered that a person has successfully passed the practical part of the knowledge test if the EPC is evaluated positively by the examination commission appointed by the Program holder.

In Denmark, an inspection of a physical building must take place during the practical part of the module for Energy Consultant I and Energy Consultant II. The physical building must be registered with a BBR application code (BBR = Building and Housing Register), where the rules for single-family houses or multi-family houses / commercial buildings, etc. must be followed.

The training courses in Malta do not include practical sessions. However, all candidates are required to attend the CPD course offered by the BICC ([Education & Training - BICC \(gov.mt\)](http://Education & Training - BICC (gov.mt))) – *Award in concepts for the decarbonisation of the building industry*. The additional course is based on a two-day seminar.

The practical component of the training program in Slovenia involves preparing two Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs): one based on actual measurements for a non-residential building and one calculated for a residential building, chosen by the candidate. These EPCs must include recommendations for energy-saving measures. Candidates are required to submit their EPCs before the exam deadline along with a slideshow presentation showcasing both case studies. Other trainees will provide online feedback on the presentations, and the EPC authors will offer explanations. The EPCs play a central role in the oral exam, where candidates defend their work in front of the evaluation committee.

The Elmhurst's ABBE 5-day training course for Domestic Energy Assessors for domestic energy assessors in UK requires five onsite assessments of residential buildings to be completed by the participants accompanied by an assessor in the last two days.

In the countries where the trainings for EPC issuers are voluntary it is up to the training provider to include a practical part in the training agenda. In Austria, the ARGE-EBA scheme includes a practical part about getting to know EPC software programmes and calculating EPCs. In most cases practical exercises are also included in the trainings provided by the calculation software companies.

6 Identified gaps in national training schemes for EPC issuers

All the countries considered in this review have different national building certification schemes, practise a different approach to training of EPC assessors, and consequently different requirements and expectations regarding the level of competence of the EPC issuers. The most objective assessment of the gaps of each national training scheme for EPC issuers against the needs of the current national building certification schemes can be made by national stakeholders. Therefore, crossCert partners have consulted at national level using various forms such as workshops; webinars, focus groups; interviews and bilateral dialogues. Detailed descriptions of the consultations conducted are presented in Appendix 3.

During the discussions in individual countries, national stakeholders have commented on both specific issues related to the training of EPC issuers and practical problems of national building certification schemes, some of which are directly related to the level of training of EPC assessors. Of course, the identified training gaps vary from country to country (see Table 7).

In most of the countries where training is mandatory - Croatia, Denmark and Slovenia - the overall assessment of the training is positive, while in Bulgaria criticism prevails, mainly due to the fact that training has been discontinued for a long period of time and the curriculum is outdated and new training materials do not reflect policy and technology developments. The general opinion of stakeholders in each of these countries was that the trainings needed more practical exercises related to energy auditing and/or certification. Both in Slovenia and in Bulgaria it is admitted that there is no official training program for the "training of trainers".

In countries where training of EPC issuers is not mandatory (Austria, Greece, Poland, Spain), it is commonly believed that the lack of training leads to lower quality certificate development. In Greece, where there was previously mandatory training, national stakeholders even found that the quality dropped dramatically after the training was dropped. However, in Poland the Ministry of Economic Development and Technology (Controlling body for all EPC-related issues) believes that studies during the education of the authorised professionals should be sufficient to form an EPCs.

Table 7- Identified gaps in national training schemes for EPC issuers

Country	Mandatory training schemes	Identified gaps in national training schemes for EPC issuers
Bulgaria	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outdated training content. The agenda for the trainings is updated for the last time in 2018. Training materials need improvement, especially in the areas of building physics and construction where specifics related to deep renovation are not included. Lectures involve too much fundamental science and do not present sufficient information about new technologies. Practical aspects related to performing an energy audit are insufficiently covered. Training of trainers is not organised to synchronise the methods of performing the trainings by different training providers and to unify the level of competence of the trainers. Building energy modelling software is outdated, not in line with the latest regulatory requirements and is limited in functions and specific training is needed about how to perform additional calculations of indicators and to correct the output.
Croatia	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear definitions and procedures (in terms of skills, datasets, and software) and manifestation of new indicators are needed. Additional training is needed on verification of savings and use of operational data for the savings as well as on zoning when modelling complex buildings. The interoperability of datasets is a crucial aspect requiring dedicated efforts.
Denmark	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessor's skills to communicate EPC report aspects and explain their utility to end-users, including potential cost savings, need further development. It is needed to introduce more practical learning during the training courses, especially in relation to deep renovation specifics. Enhance assessors' knowledge and skills related to the legal aspect. Training materials need more revisions and updates reflecting the changes in the regulations. Enhanced training is needed in relation to the ongoing digitalization process in Denmark. Specific training is needed on reducing errors to improve the quality of the EPCs.
Slovenia	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The number of presentational training hours is insignificant. The training needs to evolve accordingly with the constant changes in technology and policy and candidates need to make sure they study the most recent materials. Due to the rapidly changing policies and regulations, it has happened that candidates approached the exam having studied outdated policy & regulation. The content of the training is almost exclusively theoretical, focusing on the categorization and specifications of systems and building physics that need to be understood by the assessor/issuer to successfully issue

Country	Mandatory training schemes	Identified gaps in national training schemes for EPC issuers
		<p>an EPC; laws and regulations associated with the EPCs; the procedures and practices for issuing an EPC successfully.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Customer-centred aspects (communication & customer support) are missing in the trainings (communication & customer support). Training materials offer limited or virtually no theoretical or practical content: related to the practice of customer service or site visit/inspection; addressing the declared purpose of EPCs; communication and/or work with customers use of EPCs once they are issued. ● There is no official training program for the “training of trainers”.
Austria	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insufficient standardization and harmonization of different voluntary training courses. ● Some energy certification professionals may not have the most up-to-date knowledge on building science standards, energy efficiency technologies and regulations. ● There is no specific training on default values applied in different EPC calculation software and proper selection of these values for the building. ● There is a limited awareness on the sensitivity of an EPC calculation. ● Some EPC issuers have a limited practical experience which affects their ability to collect accurate data and provide realistic recommendations ● Special knowledge is necessary for assessment of complex buildings ● EPC issuer lack of skills to communicate complex technical information clearly to the building users. ● Cooperation among professionals is needed to develop an accurate EPC. ● Costs of training courses are high and many professionals do not participate due to this reason.
Greece	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The quality of EPCs declined significantly when training became not obligatory. ● Energy inspectors themselves, as well as other stakeholders lack of understanding of the legislation and regulations relevant to the EPCs. ● Energy inspectors do not elaborate essentially but rather typically the part EPC related to the recommendations. ● All stakeholders are confused by the differences in notions and procedures between EPC regulations and general building and tax legislation. ● There is a serious lack of knowledge even regarding legislation. ● Most of the EPC issuers do not have a satisfactory understanding of how the software properly works. Besides, software packages do not perform adequate error checking ● Building owners do not understand the value of an EPC and do not press for their good quality.
Poland	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Currently, there are no auditor retraining courses conducted in Poland, nor is there any exam to confirm auditors' knowledge. ● The main problems are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low quality of EPCs, mainly due to the lack of control by the Ministry, the lack of need for an on-site visit by the auditor - outdated knowledge of auditors - those who gained registration 10 years ago do not need to update their knowledge - small number of auditors, regardless of their level of knowledge

Country	Mandatory training schemes	Identified gaps in national training schemes for EPC issuers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of recommendations in the EPCs - an underdeveloped EPC database • Another obstacle to creating a course for auditors is the lack of official software for calculating EPCs, which would require showing multiple options for creating EPCs.
Spain	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of specific training for EPC issuers is a major gap affecting the quality of EPC assessments. • Lack of training reflects in lack of robustness resulting in decrease of EPC quality. • EPC software use or building energy performance concepts also deriving in lack of robustness. • The current regulation on academic qualifying background has to be modified to ensure that EPCs are issued by an interdisciplinary team. • The general doubts about the training courses resided on the quality and adequacy for acquiring the needed knowledge and skills around EPC issuing

7 National level recommendations for improvement of the EPC issuer trainings

During the country consultations, national stakeholders suggested many and varied improvements to the national training schemes for EPC issuers and, in some cases, to the content of the training. Many of these suggestions are country specific, but a number of recommendations can be identified that are valid in more than one country.

The inclusion in training sessions featuring information on the most recent changes in legislation related to EPCs at national and European level has been proposed in Bulgaria, Denmark, Greece, Poland and Slovenia. There is almost complete consensus on the need to provide training on new technologies and new building indicators such as IEQ and SRI, for example, as recommended in Bulgaria, Croatia, Slovenia, Austria, Greece and Spain. Experts in Bulgaria and Denmark stress that special attention should be paid to the specificities of deep renovation. More attention should be paid to the practical side of training according to national stakeholders in Bulgaria, Denmark, Austria, Greece, Poland, and in Denmark and Austria they recommend organising peer review among the experienced EPC assessors. In three countries, Bulgaria, Slovenia and Spain, it is recommended to organise trainings in separate modules for different professionals and with specific content and duration, along with the general content to be known by all EPC issuers. In Croatia and Austria, experts suggest that the training should also pay special attention to Building Information Modelling (BIM) technologies. In Denmark and Croatia there is also an emphasis on the digitisation process of EPCs, which should also be reflected in the trainings. Special emphasis on the need for EPC issuers to be able to communicate the content of EPCs to their clients is placed by national stakeholders in Slovenia, Denmark, Austria and Greece.

National stakeholders in countries that do not have mandatory training for EPC issuers agree that trainings for EPC issuers are very important. In Greece and Spain, the national stakeholders consider that training should be made mandatory. In Spain, a new regulation outlining the requirements for EPC issuers will soon be adopted. The Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge is currently developing the content for training courses. It is anticipated that training procedures will be opened up to the market, allowing regional governments to oversee the quality control of organizations providing training.

Conversely, in Poland, the Ministry of Economic Development and Technology does not intend to introduce additional courses for EPC issuers but does not rule out the introduction of courses or additional requirements after the EPBD introduces Renovation Passports and Building Logs. The introduction of an exam on building renovation knowledge is also under consideration there. In Austria, the national

stakeholders recommend harmonization of the training concepts offered by different training providers to ensure that the EPC issuers will have comparable knowledge and skills.

All recommendations at national level are summarised in Table 8 and detailed descriptions of the consultations carried out are presented in Appendix 3.

Table 8- Recommendations for improvement of EPC issuer trainings on national level

Country	Mandatory training schemes	National level recommendations for improvement
Bulgaria	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adding new lectures and develop new training materials related to new regulations, new indicators, new technologies, specifics of deep renovation. ● Optimizing the current training materials by removing parts that are already studied in the university education and adding practical aspects related to energy auditing. ● Re-design the training content and split the full list of lectures into modules specific for different specialities. ● Regulate the number of hours for each module instead of each lecture. ● Considering inclusion of the training in the regular curriculum of the technical universities. ● Introduction of practical exercises on measurements. ● The practical part of the training should cover the whole process of the energy audit starting from data collection on-site and finishing with EPC issuance. ● Upgrading and updating of the energy modelling software - improving the functionalities, presentation of final calculated results, adding new input and output data and automatic document generation. Developing new training materials and lectures related to the improved software.
Croatia	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expand the training content by adding training materials and lectures on Building Information Modelling (BIM) and its role for data collection and validation. Acknowledging the increasing influence of occupants and users in the energy certification process. ● Provide training content on new indicators, such as the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), definitions and procedures (in terms of skills, datasets, and software). ● Digitalization aspects and the interoperability of datasets is very important and accessibility to the energy model of the building for professionals and energy auditors should be provided. This topic should be timely added to the training content.
Denmark	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhance the focus on providing actionable recommendations and facilitating end-users in taking the necessary steps post-assessment. ● Emphasize how EPCs can be used for securing financing options (mandatory in Denmark), linking energy performance improvements with financial incentives. ● Encourage follow-up actions with buyers to ensure the implementation of EPC recommendations (change in EPC process) and further develop assessors' ability to communicate EPC report aspects clearly and explain their utility to end-users, including potential cost savings. Provide further guidelines and training on how to handle this in the EPC context, and in relation to the ongoing recast of EU Directives where deep renovation is in focus. ● Reintroduce Mentorship Programs that pair trainees with experienced EPC issuers for mentorship and on-the-job training to enhance practical learning.

Country	Mandatory training schemes	National level recommendations for improvement
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add practical workshops and on-site training sessions where trainees can gain hands-on experience in conducting energy assessments and using relevant tools and software. • Organise peer review systems where EPC reports are evaluated by other professionals may ensure enhanced quality and consistency. • Enhance training on legal aspects, including contract design and the consultant's responsibilities, to ensure assessors are well-versed in the regulatory framework and ISO 9001 certification requirements. • Regularly revise and update training materials to reflect any changes in EU Directives and national regulations, ensuring assessors remain well-informed and compliant with current laws, including aspects in relation to the current digitalization process in Denmark. • Strengthen the training programs to ensure a common and thorough understanding of the EPC methodology, focusing on reducing errors and increasing the overall quality of the assessments.
Slovenia	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the practical component of the training. • Re-design the training to enhance a consensus within the expert community that EPCs are not a goal in themselves but an important part for a more sustainable future (e.g. the first step to nZEBs). • Enhance the training with content highlighting customer service aspects. • Involve experts from a variety of educational backgrounds. • Frame the EPBD and EPC assessment framework as a continuously evolving field of expertise. • Develop new business models that integrate EPC assessments with other services and opportunities for customers and develop training materials on this. • Offer an EPC interpretation service. • Re-Design the training service for certification of EPC assessors in relation to: adding most recent knowledge and skills, IEQ and smart buildings; emphasize ongoing learning, enabling assessors to enhance the value of EPCs for customers. • Re-Design the training service for certification of EPC assessors in micro-credits or modules, rated from basic to advanced levels, and interconnected to optimize professional practice. • The recommended measures included in the EPCs are to be developed into a building renovation passport. Develop lectures on this topic.
Austria	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a harmonized training concept to ensure that all EPC issuers have comparable knowledge and skills. • Introduce ongoing training to ensure that professionals stay up to date concerning technical progress and knowing how to calculate new technologies in the EPC software programs. • Develop specific training content on correct usage of default values in energy modelling of buildings. • Develop specific training content on sensitivity of a EPC calculation and how it can be improved. • Organise regular exchange of experience or introduce mandatory participation in refresher training in connection to the ongoing training for technical progress and regulations. • Develop special training content on knowledge necessary for complex buildings and use of BIM. • Develop a targeted communication strategy concerning the EPC, emphasising the value, the benefits and the functions of a sound EPC

Country	Mandatory training schemes	National level recommendations for improvement
		<p>and train EPC issuers on these aspects for better communication with clients. Providing a list and descriptions of benefits to the EPC issuers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide financial support to SMEs for participation of specialised trainings for EPS issuers.
Greece	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training courses should be provided not just once but regularly. ● The training courses should include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information on electromechanical systems and technical equipment specifications to educate auditors on the latest developments in equipment. - Updates on additional building indicators (SRI, human behaviour, real consumption etc.). - Legislation and regulations relevant to EPCs, as well as their relationships with general building legislation / regulations - EPCs software and the TOTEE (Technical Instructions of the Technical Chamber of Greece). - Theoretical knowledge but also on site and hands on training. - Exams every 3-5 years ● Alongside the formal training, awareness campaigns or specialized informational activities should be targeted at the general public and other stakeholders. ● Developing regularly updated material (e.g. FAQs, wiki), clarifying details for inspectors and other stakeholders. ● Developing a separate work environment for self-training within the EPCs Registry to be used by energy inspectors test their work before uploading their EPCs to the 'formal' Registry. ● EPCs should be issued by a team of energy inspectors with different profiles, each one specialized to a sector, who could complement each other, especially when it comes to large and complex buildings.
Poland	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training courses for EPC issuers should include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy efficiency in construction - EU directives, the Thermal Modernization Law, implementing regulations, basic information - Issues of building physics - Planning of building modernization - EPCs software - Calculation examples ● In addition, each auditor should update his knowledge and pass a knowledge exam every 5 years.
Spain	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introducing a regular and compulsory training for all EPC certifiers, including a longer first training cycle covering basics of handling and calculating the world of EPC followed by regular shorter training sessions to refresh all the basic concepts. ● The training of professionals to be organised around the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in national or European Building Performance Acts - State-of-the-art technologies. - Deep energy renovation recommendations. - Common mistakes or errors in EPCs. - Funding programs for renovation and their technical requirements. - Consumer information and communication. - Design of contract between the EPC issuer and the customer. - Further (soft) skills for EPC assessors.

Country	Mandatory training schemes	National level recommendations for improvement
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is more coherent to ensure that EPCs are issued by an interdisciplinary team. Different profiles of professionals should be considered to develop specific training contents.

8 Recommendations for improvement of the EPC issuers trainings to reflect changes in the European regulations

The topic of trainings for EPC issuers has been addressed in several research projects focused on the next generation of EPCs, albeit as an element of other analyses related to improving the quality of EPC issuers (*QualDeEPC* project), with research on the EPC generation process (*TIMEPAC* project) or on assessor qualification requirements (*EUBSuperHub* project). *QualDeEPC* and *TIMEPAC* come up with similar recommendations to introduce mandatory training and/or mandatory testing of EPC issuers. Moreover, the *QualDeEPC* experts recommend specific text for the EPBD to require EU countries to introduce mandatory initial and periodic training at national level or periodic testing of EPC assessors⁵. *QualDeEPC* also recommends content of regular training for EPC assessors and a proposal for a peer review of the quality of a sample of EPCs issued by an assessor as part of the training⁶. The recommended content of regular training is as follows:

- changes in national or European Building Performance Acts,
- state-of-the-art technologies,
- deep energy renovation recommendations,
- common mistakes or errors in EPCs,
- funding programs for renovation and their technical requirements,
- consumer information and communication,
- contract design,
- further (soft) skills for EPC assessors.

The *crossCert* project partners conducted an analysis of the proposals of the various *Next-generation EPC* cluster research projects, including *QualDeEPC*'s proposal to conduct periodic trainings for EPC issuers⁷. All the experts involved in cross testing agree that it is highly beneficial to provide regular and mandatory training to Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) issuers, irrespective of the training practices currently followed in their respective countries. To mitigate some identified potential risks, the experts have made the following recommendations:

- Balance between the frequency and intensity of training sessions is very important, providing cost-effective training solutions, and ensuring that training programmes are focused on educational objectives without becoming overly bureaucratic.
- Regular training sessions should be concise, flexible, and highly targeted to the needs of EPC issuers and avoid unnecessary topics.
- Designing cost-effective training and providing funding for training to EPC issuers or financing EPCs to building owners can help prevent the increased cost of EPCs due to mandatory and regular training.

⁵ Thomas, S., M. Venjakob. (2023) Conclusive policy recommendations guide. EU level and general policy recommendations to Member States. p. 31. https://qualdeepc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/QualDeEPC_D7-2_PolicyRecommendationsGuide_230224_v2.pdf

⁶ Korma, E. (2023) Guidebook for improved EPCs presenting the project's proposal for an enhanced and converging EPC assessment and certification scheme. Section 2.4. https://qualdeepc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/QualDeEPC_D5.3_Guidebook-for-improved-EPCs_V2_final_28.02.2023.pdf

⁷ Gómez, A., N. Fueyo. (2023) Cross testing of first generation of new EPCs. Section 4.6.

- Regular training should not be replaced by a periodic evaluation of EPC issuers. However, self-testing, such as completing predefined online tests, can be a valuable addition to regular training and may serve as a viable strategy to enhance the capacities of EPC issuers.

Cross testers have provided positive feedback to *QualDeEPC* proposal regarding the content of periodic training. Furthermore, they suggest that some topics should be emphasised, namely:

- Deep energy renovation recommendations – identifying and assessing a range of energy efficiency measures and developing customised retrofit plans.
- Communication skills – to communicate effectively the various aspects of the EPC report and their usefulness to the user, including the financial implications of the recommended renovations.
- New indicators – latest indicators that are at the time being used to assess buildings, such as SRI and IEQ.
- Energy consumption measurement – to help EPC assessors improve the accuracy of their energy performance assessments.
- The next steps follow an EPC – e.g. one-stop shops, and energy efficiency retrofits, among others. EPC assessors can help their clients to make better-informed decisions by providing such comprehensive advice.
- Elaboration of packages of measures instead of presenting isolated measures – the creation of renovation plans for individual buildings would help EPC assessors provide their clients with a more effective approach towards achieving energy efficiency.

As the results of other *crossCert* project studies have shown, the differences in EPC assessment processes and methodologies across European countries are significant⁸, both in terms of the data used and the detail of the building assessments and tools used. It is therefore very important to find the optimal balance between the complexity of the assessment and the required knowledge and skills of EPC assessors, which is not the case in some countries as noted in an analysis by researchers at *Heriot-Watt University* in Edinburgh, UK⁹. The EC's ambitions are to achieve better harmonisation of certificates and convergence of national assessment methodologies for energy performance and building certification through the next generation of EPCs. Researchers in *Next-generation EPC* cluster projects propose a range of policies and tools to improve the quality of certificates, summarised and analysed separately in the *crossCert* project¹⁰. Some of these recommendations might make assessments more accurate and reliable, but at the expense of applying methodologies with greater complexity. This means that a higher level of qualification of EPC assessors is needed and consequently undergoing mandatory training and verification of knowledge and skills. On the other hand, there are many buildings with simple technical systems where more sophisticated assessment is practically unnecessary. A sensible approach is to introduce different qualification level requirements for EPC assessors when assessing buildings of different complexity and develop different training programmes accordingly.

⁸ Sayfekar, M., D. Jenkins. (2022) Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states. *crossCert* project Deliverable 3.1, DEC 2022. Online: https://www.crosscert.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/crossCert_D3.1_Review_of_approaches_to_EPC_assessment_v4.4.pdf

⁹ Jenkins, D., M. Sayfekar. (2023) Investigating the relationship between energy assessor training and assessment methodology in standardised energy assessments in Europe.

¹⁰ Gómez, A., N. Fueyo, (2024) Cross testing of first generation of new EPCs. *crossCert* project Deliverable 2.6, FEB 2024.

8.1 Recommendations for initial training of EPC issuers

The analysis of practices in different countries with regard to the training of EPC issuers and the proposals for the next generation of EPC leads us to make the following recommendations to those responsible for developing specialised initial national training schemes, whether mandatory or voluntary.

Scope and form of trainings:

Training sessions should be conducted separately for EPC issuers of buildings with varying levels of qualification. This necessitates the introduction of regulations tailored to different levels of EPC issuers. Each training course should be customized in terms of content and duration to align with the specific qualifications and skills required by participants. Examples of the desired knowledge and skills for EPC issuers can be found in the training schemes of Croatia and Denmark (refer to Appendix 2).

Certification of complex buildings, which involve multiple building systems, demands a higher level of expertise and should be undertaken by an interdisciplinary team of EPC issuers. Therefore, it is advisable to organize separate training modules for the certification of complex buildings, catering to professionals with diverse specialties. These modules should vary in content and duration based on the roles and responsibilities of the professionals involved in the EPC assessment process. In addition to specialist modules, generic modules covering essential knowledge and skills that all EPC issuers should possess, irrespective of their specialization, should be included. A practical exercise module, ideally conducted towards the end of the training, should involve participants working in interdisciplinary teams to certify suitable existing buildings. Attendance for the practical part should be mandatory, while theoretical lectures could be delivered online, with specialist modules running in parallel.

Training on the certification of complex buildings should culminate in an examination. The exam should consist of two parts: the first part assessing knowledge acquired during theoretical lectures, with different exam content for EPC issuers with distinct specialties; and the second part requiring interdisciplinary teams to present their certification work on test buildings to an examination commission. This commission may comprise representatives from the training provider, trainers from other EPC issuer courses, national supervisory authorities, experienced EPC issuers, but also not qualified EPC users to evaluate participant's communication skills.

For buildings with simpler systems, certification can be conducted by an individual EPC issuer. Training for certifying these buildings should follow a shorter curriculum, including a practical component related to certifying a suitable existing building. The training schemes should be structured in a way that allows EPC issuers of buildings with simple systems to progress to certification of complex buildings without repetition of training and exams on topics that are already covered.

Trainings content:

The training content should be carefully curated, ensuring a well-balanced selection of topics. It is essential to exclude basic scientific concepts that participants have likely already covered in their professional education. The primary focus should be on elucidating the practical application of this scientific knowledge in the context of assessing the energy performance of buildings and evaluating the impact of implementing various energy-saving measures. This information should be categorised into general and specialised modules tailored to different professional backgrounds.

Recurring training topics, such as state-of-the-art technologies, deep energy renovation recommendations, new indicators, consumer information and communication, funding programs for renovation, and next steps following an EPC, are highly relevant in today's context and should be integrated into the initial training programs for EPC issuers. The first two topics could be condensed in the general module and explored in greater detail in the specialized modules, while the remaining topics are suitable for inclusion in the general module. Additionally, the general module should cover legislation pertinent to EPC assessments, a step-by-step description of the assessment process, types of documents, data sources, an overview of tools utilised, and other related aspects. It is crucial to periodically update and supplement the initial training content to align with the current material covered in recurring training

sessions. This approach ensures that young EPC issuers acquire a comprehensive set of knowledge and skills necessary for their professional roles.

The practical module should encompass exercises focused on utilising national EPC software and other tools for evaluating new indicators, conducting various types of measurements essential for EPC assessments, and simulating the entire building certification process. This process should commence with the collection and processing of input data and culminate in the preparation of all requisite documentation for an actual building. Certifying a complex building necessitates collaboration within interdisciplinary teams, guided by experienced EPC assessors. Subsequently, the final outcomes should be presented and defended before the examination commission.

8.2 Recommendations for periodical training of EPC issuers

It is recommended that periodic follow-up training sessions for EPC issuers should be conducted at least once every two years, with online delivery being the preferred method. This approach will help reduce training costs and minimize the time participants need to invest. These training sessions can be designed to cater to professionals from various fields and different levels of EPC issuers, as long as the topics covered are relevant to their expertise.

The scheduling of recurrent training should be flexible, offering courses at different intervals, durations, and content based on the current needs of EPC issuers. The content of the first recurrent trainings for already accredited EPC issuers should align with the recommendations of the *QualDeEPC* project complemented by the suggestions of the cross testers in *crossCert* project as described above. Subsequent trainings should present updated content on these and other topics that may come up.

In case of significant methodological changes, it is advisable to conduct face-to-face courses with a practical component, similar to the initial training but with a shorter agenda focusing on the revised methodology.

The content of these sessions should be used to periodically enhance and supplement the curriculum and training materials for the foundational training.

To enhance the efficiency of the recurrent training process for EPC issuers, establishing a national online platform where all training providers can announce upcoming sessions, and EPC issuers can register and receive automatic email notifications, is recommended. Registration for these sessions should be centralised through this platform, which can also serve as a national registry of completed trainings for every EPC issuer.

9 Conclusion

The analysis of training and education services for certified EPC issuers across Europe highlights the importance of structured and standardised training in ensuring the quality and reliability of Energy Performance Certificates. While certification processes differ across countries, common challenges and opportunities have been identified. Addressing these issues through improved training frameworks is crucial to aligning EPC issuance with the European Union's energy efficiency and decarbonisation goals.

This study highlights the considerable variation in training requirements among EU member states. Some countries mandate formal education and certification, while others operate on a more voluntary basis. This lack of consistency can result in discrepancies in EPC accuracy, impacting consumer trust and the effectiveness of EPCs as a policy tool for promoting energy efficiency. Establishing minimum training standards at the EU level could help bridge these gaps and enhance the reliability of EPC assessments.

One critical aspect of EPC training is the need for more practical, hands-on learning experiences. Many existing programmes focus heavily on theoretical knowledge while neglecting the practical skills required for accurate building assessments. Introducing mentorship programmes, on-site training, and peer review systems could enhance the competency of EPC issuers. Simulating real-life scenarios and providing exposure to fieldwork would contribute to improved quality and consistency in EPC issuance.

With the growing emphasis on deep renovations and digital tools such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), training programmes must adapt to include these competencies. The digitalisation of the EPC process presents an opportunity to modernise training curricula, ensuring that EPC issuers are well-equipped to use advanced assessment tools effectively. Training should also cover the implications of evolving EU regulations on building performance, helping EPC issuers stay up to date with policy changes.

Effective communication skills have also emerged as a key area for improvement. EPC issuers must be able to clearly explain the significance of EPCs to end-users, providing guidance on how to act upon recommendations. A well-structured EPC should not only present energy performance data but also empower building owners and occupants to take meaningful steps towards improving efficiency. Strengthening assessors' ability to engage with clients and convey technical findings in an accessible manner will be essential to increasing the impact of EPCs.

In conclusion, improving the training and education of EPC issuers is vital to enhancing the effectiveness of EPCs in driving energy efficiency. By standardising training requirements, incorporating more practical experience, embracing digital advancements, and strengthening communication skills, EPC issuers will be better prepared to support Europe's energy transition. Future policy initiatives should prioritise these areas to create a more robust and reliable EPC system that benefits all stakeholders, from policymakers to end-users.

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Polish online registry of EPC issuers: <https://rejestrcheb.mrit.gov.pl/rejestr-uprawnionych>

UK registry of EPS assessors. <https://www.theepcregister.co.uk/>

Zeus database: Salzburg, Styria, Carinthia, Burgenland, Lower Austria and Tyrol.

(<https://www.energieausweise.net/>)

11 Appendix 1. Questionnaire on trainings for EPC issuers

1. General requirements for EPC issuers:

- 1.1. *What are the educational background and experience requirements for EPC issuers?*
- 1.2. *Are there different levels of competence required for the EPC issuers for different type of buildings? If yes, what are these different levels and for which types of buildings?*
- 1.3. *What are the requirements for EPC issuers regarding completed specialized professional training?*
- 1.4. *Which are the regulatory acts setting up the requirements for EPC issuers regarding: 1) Education; 2). Professional experience, and 3) Specialized training?*

2. Conduction of specialized trainings for EPS issuers

- 2.1. *Who has the duty/right to conduct trainings and issue documents for successful graduates?*
- 2.2. *How often are organised trainings? Is there any regulation about this?*
- 2.3. *Are there any requirements regarding the frequency of participation in specialized trainings?*
- 2.4. *Who is allowed to participate in the trainings?*
- 2.5. *What are the criteria for successfully completed training? Are there any exams?*
- 2.6. *If there are exams, who conducts it? Is there any formal commission set for the exams?*
- 2.7. *How often the EPC issuers should pass exams? Is it possible to go to an exam only or it is related to participation in training?*
- 2.8. *Is there a regulated fee for participation in training? Or for participation in an exam?*
- 2.9. *Is it regulated what kind of document is issued to graduates?*
- 2.10. *Is there an official register of graduates? Who keeps the registry?*
- 2.11. *Are the trainings in other EU member countries recognized and under what conditions?*

3. Content of the specialized training for EPC issuers

- 3.1. *Is there a regulation about the curriculum content and scope of the trainings? Where is it regulated? Could you provide the document in the shared folder or a link?*
- 3.2. *What are the general topics included in the training? How many hours is the total length of the training and how many hours is the length of the lectures on each of the general topics?*
- 3.3. *Is the training content have a practical part? What does it include?*

12 Appendix 2. Nationally regulated content of the training programs for EPC issuers

Content of the training program for EPC issuers in Bulgaria

No.	Content of the training for energy auditors – Level 1 consultants	Lectures
1.	Module 1: Energy auditing and energy performance certification of buildings	71
1.1.	Structure, development, and comparative framework of European and Bulgarian energy efficiency legislation. Succession and specific requirements of the energetic efficiency norms. Legally binding norms of laws and ordinances in the field of energy efficiency.	2
1.2.	Nomenclature of building types in Bulgaria. Construction systems, practices, and trends in building construction. Assessment of the efficiency of the systems in the context of energy consumption in buildings. Specificities of the building envelope, identification of data sources. Features and techniques in surveying and measuring geometrical characteristics in energy auditing. Applicable technical standards.	2
1.3.	Substantial requirements to the buildings, normative assurance for their application and control on their performance in the buildings. Definition of "life cycle" and "intended use" of construction products for buildings. Substantial characteristics of construction products for the building envelope, which have direct relation to the requirement for energy efficiency of the buildings.	2
1.4.	Principles of heat transfer. Heat transfer through construction elements. Features of the heat transfer coefficient (U- value, W/m ² K) at different constructive elements of the building. Reference sources for calculation and/or identification of U- values.	2
1.5.	Thermal bridges. Ways for assessment of the heat losses through building envelope elements with thermal bridges.	1
1.6.	Measurement of hydraulic, thermal and electrical values; consumption of: energy, solid, liquid and gaseous substances.	2
1.7.	Stages, content, and features of the energy audit in building. Reference data sources, systematization and documentation of the output data and results. Sensitivity analysis of the results. Modern measurement equipment applied in energy auditing of buildings. Control measurement points. Integration and analysis of results. Documenting the measurement.	5
1.8.	Method БДС EN ISO 13790 for determination of annual energy consumption in buildings. Specific definitions and concepts. Heat loses and gains. Energy balance of building. Components of heat and energy balance, systemic connections, mutual influence and reconciliation of the components of the heat flows. Optimal energy cost concept.	3
1.9.	Nature and capabilities of the building modelling. Engineering principles for determination of thermal zones in a building. Energy modelling software basics and features.	2
1.10.	Approach and specificities in creating of building energy models for the heating period. Modelling of energy consumption and mutual influence of the heating and ventilations systems at buildings with one or more thermal zones. Variants and concepts of models, evaluation of models.	2
1.11.	Approach and specificities in creating of building energy models for the cooling period. Modelling of energy consumption at combined operation of cooling systems. Variants and concepts of models, evaluation of models.	2

No.	Content of the training for energy auditors – Level 1 consultants	Lectures
1.12.	Evaluation of the effect from single energy saving measures. Iterative process of evaluation of the efficiency of a package of energy saving measures. Compatibility of energy saving measures with the main (essential) requirements to the buildings.	2
1.13.	Principles and rules for energy efficiency in the main of building subsystem groups:	
1.13.1.	Fuels. Water boilers using conventional energy resources. Biomass boilers. Seasonal efficiency of boilers. Evaluation of the efficiency of local heating with fireplaces and individual heating devices with solid, liquid, and gaseous fuel combustion. Applicable norms, rules, and technical specifications.	3
1.13.2.	Gas supply to public buildings. Efficiency of the systems in the context of technology development.	2
1.13.3.	Combined heat and power equipment	2
1.13.3a	Sub-stations for district heat supply for heating and domestic hot water. Control of thermal processes. Features of control equipment. Distribution of heat in buildings. Distribution and measurement of heat for domestic hot water.	2
1.13.4.	Energy efficiency of pumps and fans. Factors affecting efficiency.	2
1.13.5.	Assessment of energy efficiency opportunities for heating systems, implemented by classic schemes. Effective technologies of heating systems with conventional heat source. Evaluation of the efficiency of systems if the energy saving measures provide different levels of heat comfort in the building. Specific requirements in the corresponding national legislation, European standards, and norms.	3
1.13.6.	Heating, air conditioning or ventilation building systems with non-conventional energy sources. Heat pumps.	2
	Modern air conditioning systems for public buildings. Systems for special purpose buildings. Requirements in the respective national legislation, European standards and norms.	3
1.13.7.	<p>Solar energy systems.</p> <p>Active thermal solar systems. Applicable schemes of systems for domestic hot water production in buildings with central heating systems. Method for assessment of the possible share of solar energy. Market conditions and current elements and facilities for installations in buildings.</p> <p>Active solar cooling systems. Types and efficiency indicators.</p> <p>Active solar systems for electricity production. Method for evaluation of the quantity of electricity produced from solar energy. Market conditions and current elements and facilities for installations in buildings.</p>	<p>2</p> <p>2</p> <p>2</p>
1.13.8.	Cooling and freezing systems. Types by functionality. Indicators for evaluation of the efficiency of the systems.	2
1.13.9.	Electrical equipment and power supply systems in public buildings. Specific requirements in the respective national legislation, European standards and norms.	2
1.13.10	Modern lighting systems. Evaluation of efficiency and energy consumption at combined operation of active artificial lighting systems and systems for increased use of daylight. Indicators for efficiency of lighting systems in buildings. Specific requirements in the respective national legislation, European standards and norms.	3

No.	Content of the training for energy auditors – Level 1 consultants	Lectures
1.14.	Efficiency of appliances consuming electricity in buildings. Requirements in the respective national and European legislation, European standards and norms.	2
1.15.	Modern technologies and systems for monitoring, control and management of energy consumption in public buildings. Requirements in the respective national legislation, European standards and norms.	2
1.16.	Passive buildings and nearly zero energy buildings. Affinities and differences of Concepts. National legislation, European standards and norms.	2
1.17.	Feasibility evaluation of energy saving measures. Indicators for economic feasibility. Specialized software for economic rating of energy saving measures.	2
1.18.	Energy Performance Certificate of building. Types of certificates, normative terms, and conditions for certification.	2
1.19.	Report on the results from inspection of water boilers. Report on the results from inspection of air conditioning installations.	2

No.	Content of the training for energy auditors – Level 2 consultants	Lectures
1.	Module 1: Energy auditing and energy performance certification of buildings	50
1.1.	European framework and national legislation for energy efficiency in buildings, policies and measures. Technical norms and rules for energy efficiency in buildings in Bulgaria. Basic requirements for buildings. Performance indicators of construction products to achieve the energy performance of buildings.	2
1.2.	Types of residential buildings, overview of technical norms and construction systems for residential buildings. Influence and connectivity of construction systems with energy consumption in buildings. Features of building envelope structures, identification of data sources. Peculiarities in surveying and measuring geometrical characteristics for the purposes of energy auditing. Applicable technical standards.	2
1.3.	Principles of heat transfer. Heat transfer through construction elements. Features of the heat transfer coefficient (U- value, W/m ² K) at different constructive elements of the building. Effect of thermal bridges on heat transfer through the structure. Reference sources for calculation and/or identification of U- values.	2
1.4.	Measurement of hydraulic, thermal and electrical values; consumption of: energy, solid, liquid and gaseous substances.	2
1.5.	Technical means of measurement during energy audits in buildings.	2
1.6.	Stages, content, and features of the energy audit in building. Specifics in the auditing of residential buildings. Identification of acceptable data sources, systematization and documentation of the output data and results.	4
1.7.	Standardised method for determination of annual energy consumption in buildings (БДС EN ISO 13790 or equivalent). Specific definitions and concepts. Heat losses and gains. Energy balance of building. Components of heat and energy balance, systemic connections, mutual influence and reconciliation of the components of the heat flows.	3
1.8.	Basics and features of the energy modelling software for buildings.	4

No.	Content of the training for energy auditors – Level 2 consultants	Lectures
1.9.	Principles and rules for energy efficiency in the main of building subsystem groups:	
1.9.1.	Fuels. Water boilers using conventional energy resources. Biomass boilers. Seasonal efficiency of boilers. Evaluation of the efficiency of local heating with fireplaces and individual heating devices with solid, liquid, and gaseous fuel combustion used in dwellings	3
1.9.2.	Gas supply to dwellings in multi-family buildings.	2
1.9.3.	Sub-stations for district heat supply for heating and domestic hot water. Control of thermal processes. Features of control equipment. Distribution of heat in residential buildings. Distribution and measurement of heat for heating in dwellings. Distribution and measurement of heat for domestic hot water.	2
1.9.4.	Energy efficiency of pumps and fans. Factors affecting efficiency.	2
1.9.5.	Systems with non-conventional energy sources. Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning building systems in residential buildings in mixed-use buildings of the fifth construction category.	2
1.9.6.	Heat pumps	2
1.9.7.	Solar energy systems. Applicable schemes of systems for domestic hot water production in buildings with central heating systems. Method for assessment of the possible share of solar energy. Active solar systems for electricity production. Method for evaluation of the quantity of electricity produced from solar energy. Market conditions and current elements and facilities for installations in buildings.	2 2
1.9.8.	Electrical equipment and lighting systems.	2
1.9.9.	Efficiency of appliances consuming electricity in buildings. Requirements in the respective national and European legislation, European standards and norms.	1
1.10.	Feasibility evaluation of energy saving measures. Indicators for economic feasibility. Specialized software for economic rating of energy saving measures.	2
1.11.	Energy Performance Certificates of buildings. Templates for new and existing buildings, regulatory rules for certification. Preparation of Energy Performance Certificates of buildings.	2
1.12.	Report on the results from inspection of water boilers.	1

Requirements for the training program for EPC issuers in Denmark

Theoretical Basic Module

Knowledge to be obtained

The trained person can show an overview of and, to the extent necessary, can describe in detail:

- Rules, guidelines and tools that are common to the energy labelling scheme, including the building regulations, calculation tools, rules on the consultant's responsibility, competence and impartiality as well as "Energy solutions for climate screens and installations" from the Knowledge Center for Energy Savings in Buildings.
- Construction, insulating ability (taking into account any thermal bridges), tightness and b-factors of and for the climate screen incl. roof structure, external walls, external doors (without glass), foundation, ground cover, basement external walls and deck over unheated basement. Because these structures are to a certain extent hidden, registration, if necessary, must be done on the basis of qualified judgement. The trained person must therefore have knowledge of usual construction practices for the relevant building type and year of construction.
- Orientation, structure, insulating capacity, tightness, light and shadow conditions of/for windows and exterior doors with glass. The educated must, among other things, be able to distinguish between older double glazing and newer "energy glazing" with and without a "warm edge", respectively between ordinary glass and energy glass in front windows/connected windows.
- Type and efficiency of heat sources. The trained person must be able to distinguish between a significant number of different boiler types, heat exchanger types, heat pump types, etc.
- The energy labelling scheme's special rules for the treatment of supplementary heat sources, e.g. wood stoves.
- Heat distribution system, including losses that are deposited outside the climate screen, and required supply temperatures for waterborne space heating.
- Hot water tank and distribution system for domestic hot water.
- B-factors for the individual elements in installations for space heating and domestic hot water.
- Electricity consumption for pumps in the heating system. The trained person must be able to distinguish between different pumps that are found in the Danish building stock.
- Renewable energy installations including solar heating, solar cells, household wind turbines, heat pumps, etc.
- Type of ventilation system and typical heat loss, including efficiency of any heat recovery. Electricity consumption for mechanical ventilation/extraction. The trainee must be able to distinguish between a significant number of different types of air transport facilities.
- Estimated prices for and potential savings from energy renovation measures

Skills to be obtained -theoretical part

The educated can

- Analyse the conditions in a building that influence the energy performance
- use the calculation tools associated with the scheme.
- Use historical drawing material and possibly other documentation, e.g. in relation to registration of the climate screen's structure, insulation capacity, etc., as these constructions are to a certain extent hidden

Basic Module, Energy consultant I (single-family houses)

The course has a scope of 7 days

Knowledge to be obtained

The trained person can show an overview of and, to the extent necessary, can describe in detail

- The overall requirements for a certified energy labelling company
- The procedure for the Danish Energy Agency's supervisory cases, technical audit
- The procedure for preparing the various types of energy labels, e.g. within new construction and energy labelling according to actual consumption
- Latest measures within the scheme
- Latest quality figures within the scheme
- Typical errors in the energy labelling reports
- The requirements for competence and impartiality in relation to new construction and energy labelling

Skills to be obtained

The educated can

- Analyse and record (including measuring) the conditions in a single-family house that influence the energy performance, cf. knowledge from the common basic module and the above, and report the information in electronic form in a standardised energy labelling report
- Assess the relevance and quality of the automatically generated savings proposals in the calculation tool in relation to architectural conditions, practical feasibility, indoor climate, comfort, user behaviour, estimated costs for execution, savings potential, etc.
- Propose and assess the relevance and quality of additional savings proposals in addition to the automatically generated ones, e.g. by integrating better architectural quality, lifetime-related need for replacement of building parts, combinations of measures that provide better cost-effectiveness and/or by other adaptations that are relevant in the situation in question
- Prepare an energy labelling report, including selecting the most relevant proposals and describing the proposals in precise and easy-to-understand prose
- Communicate clearly the purpose and content of the energy labelling scheme for single-family houses to the building owner, including, inter alia, the profitability of the savings proposals
- Take responsibility for own advice
- Acquire new knowledge in the field and enter into professional and interdisciplinary collaboration with a professional approach

Energy Consultant II

The module presupposes either a passed Basic Module with the specialisation Energy Consultant I or a passed training course regarding the BedreBolig scheme's benefit package 1, cf. executive order on an approval scheme for companies that provide consultancy and project management, etc. in connection with energy renovation of homes.

The course has a scope of 3 days of teaching of 7 lessons and an exam

Knowledge to be obtained

The trained person can show an overview of and, to the extent necessary, describe in detail

- Rules that specifically deal with multi-family houses with regard to energy consumption and indoor climate, including energy label according to actual consumption
- Installations in larger buildings (larger ventilation systems, larger RE plants, etc.), condition and efficiency of heat recovery systems for buildings' installations. The trained person must be able to distinguish between a significant number of different types of installations
- Type of cooling system and typical heat loss, including condition, efficiency of any heat recovery. The trained person must be able to distinguish between a significant number of different types of installations
- Lighting system (lighting fixtures and controls, etc.) The trained person must be able to distinguish between different types of lighting fixtures and controls, etc.

Skills to be obtained

- Analyse and record (including measure) the conditions in a multi-family house that have an influence on the energy performance, cf. knowledge from the common Basic Module, Energy Consultant I and the above, and report the information in electronic form in a standardised energy labelling report
- Assess the relevance and quality of the automatically generated savings proposals in the calculation tool in relation to architectural conditions, practical feasibility, indoor climate, comfort, user behaviour, estimated costs for execution, savings potential, etc.
- Propose and assess the relevance and quality of additional savings proposals in addition to the automatically generated ones, e.g. by integrating better architectural quality,
- Lifetime-related need for replacement of building parts, combinations of measures that provide better cost-effectiveness and/or by other adaptations that are relevant in the situation in question
- Prepare an energy labelling report for a multi-family house, including selecting the most relevant proposals and describing the proposals in precise and easy-to-understand prose
- Communicate clearly and clearly the purpose and content of the energy labelling scheme for multi-family houses to the building owner, including, among other things, the profitability of the savings proposals
- Take responsibility for own advice
- Acquire new knowledge in the field and engage in professional and interdisciplinary collaboration with a professional approach.

Update Module

Both single-family house consultants and multi-family house consultants must pass the update module / course with a maximum of 3 years interval. The time is calculated from the most recently passed course. If this does not happen, the energy consultant must not prepare and report energy labels in the period until the update course has been passed.

Knowledge to be obtained

The trained person can show an overview of and, to the extent necessary, describe

- The specific learning objectives for Energy Consultant I (single-family houses) and Energy Consultant II (multi-family houses)
- New rules and notices within the energy labelling scheme
- Latest measures within the scheme, including new methods and tools
- Latest quality figures within the scheme

- Typical errors in the energy labelling reports

Skills to be obtained

The educated can

- Apply previous and new provisions, methods and tools
- Convey clearly and clearly the purpose and content of the energy labelling scheme for single-family houses and multi-family houses to the building owner, including e.g. the profitability of the savings proposals
- Take responsibility for your own advice
- Acquire new knowledge in the field and engage in professional and interdisciplinary collaboration with a professional approach.

Content of the training programme for the independent experts - issuers of energy performance certificates in Slovenia

1. Energy performance certificate regulations
 - 1.1 EU legislation
 - 1.2. Regulations governing the design of buildings
 - 1.3. Regulations governing the production and issue of energy performance certificates
2. Determination of the energy performance of buildings
 - 2.1 Thermodynamic processes
 - 2.2. Types of buildings, building furniture, appliances and systems
 - 2.3. Energy efficiency of installations and systems
 - 2.4. Methodology for the production of an energy performance certificate and methodology for the determination of indicators in energy performance certificate (measured, calculated)
 - 2.5. Evaluation of energy consumption data
 - 2.6. Examples of implemented energy efficient buildings
3. Measures to increase energy efficiency
 - 3.1. Consultancy skills in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings
 - 3.2. Measures to improve the quality of the building envelope
 - 3.3. Measures to improve the energy efficiency of building energy management systems
 - 3.4. Measures for the use of renewable energy sources
 - 3.5 Organisational measures
 - 3.6. Case studies of measures to increase energy efficiency
4. Process for carrying out a building survey for the purpose of drawing up an energy performance certificate
 - 4.1. Instructions for the use of the energy performance certificate manual or instructions for use of the computer tool
 - 4.2. Inventory and review of the building documentation
 - 4.3. Visual and functional inspection of the building
 - 4.4. Preparation of advice on measures
 - 4.5. Production and issue of energy performance certificates
 - 4.6. Examples of energy performance certificates produced
 - 4.7. Communication with customers
5. Practical implementation of the production and issue of an energy performance certificate
 - 5.1. Individual implementation of the production and issue of an energy performance certificate with the production of a report
 - 5.2. Presentation of the elaborated energy performance certificates

Requirements for the training program for EPC issuers in Croatia

Required knowledge and skills:

After successfully completing the training programme, authorised persons must:

- Understand the key settings of the European strategic and legislative framework for energy efficiency, including the European energy efficiency directives,
- Have a good knowledge of the applicable regulations implementing energy efficiency directives in the Republic of Croatia,
- Be capable of independently collecting and processing building data and technical systems necessary for energy assessment according to the methodology of conducting an energy audit prescribed by the Ordinance on Energy Audit of Buildings and Energy Certification,
- Apply computer programs intended for the implementation of the necessary calculations for the purpose of obtaining data that are expressed in the conducted energy certification and energy audit of the building,
- Evaluate the method of energy management in the building,
- Assess the building characteristics of the building in terms of rational use of energy and thermal protection,
- Evaluate the technical systems of the building,
- Interpret data on the building in particular in relation to the dimensions and type of building parts of the building,
- Perform the necessary calculations related to the data necessary for the implementation of energy certification and energy audit of the building,
- Determine measures to improve the energy efficiency of the building and make recommendations for the use of the building or determine measures to improve the energy efficiency of heating and cooling or air conditioning systems in the building, electrical and domestic hot water systems,
- Prepare an energy certificate of the building, a report on the conducted energy audit of the building and a report on regular inspection of the heating and cooling systems or air conditioning systems in the building.

Module 1. Training program for persons conducting energy certification and energy audits of buildings with simple technical system – includes 36 hours of classes and 4 hours for the exam covering following subjects:

1. Regulations in the field of energy efficiency, energy audits and energy certification of buildings – 4 hours
2. Basics of energy and building physics – 3 hours
3. Basics of buildings, construction of buildings – 4 hours
4. Heating systems – 10 hours
5. Electric lighting in the building – 2 hours
6. Implementation of energy audit of the building and technical heating system – 3 hours
7. Practical classes – implementation of the energy audit of the building, preparation of the energy certificate of the building and reports on regular inspection of simple technical systems in the building – 10 hours

Module 2. Training program for persons conducting energy certification and energy audits of buildings with complex technical system

For architectural and construction profession – includes 20 hours of classes and 4 hours for the exam covering following subjects:

1. Energy efficiency regulations – 2 hours
2. Physics of the building and complex structures of the building parts – 8 hours
3. Materials – 2 hours
4. Building envelope systems – 2 hours
5. Practical teaching – Implementation of energy audit of the building with complex technical system and independent usable units of the building, preparation of reports, energy certificates and recommendations – 6 hours
6. Exam lasting 4 hours includes theoretical and practical part

For mechanical engineering profession – includes 26 hours of classes and 4 hours for the exam:

1. Energy efficiency regulations – 2 hours
2. Heating, cooling and ventilation systems – 16 hours
3. Practical teaching – Implementation of energy audit of buildings with complex technical system, regular inspection of heating systems and cooling and air conditioning systems, preparation of reports and recommendations – 8 hours
4. Exam theoretical and practical part – 4 hours

For electrical engineering profession – includes 12 hours of classes and 4 hours for the exam:

1. Energy efficiency regulations – 2 hours
2. Electric lighting in the building – 3 hours
3. Renewable energy sources, system testing and review (classification, standards and norms, characteristics, losses, degrees of utility), methodology of calculation and selection of system elements, application schemes and regulation systems, assessment of consumption and efficiency of the system – 2 hours
5. Building control and automation systems (room, zone, building, CNUS) – 2 hours
6. Practical classes – Conducting energy audit of buildings with a complex technical system, preparing reports and recommendations – 3 hours
7. Exam theoretical and practical part – 4 hours

Training programme for authorised persons (Refinement program)

The training program for authorised persons is determined in the duration of 8 to 16 hours depending on the technical, technological and methodological progress in the field of energy efficiency in buildings, changes in regulations and the development of computer tools.

Authorized persons shall acquire knowledge of:

- Reports on energy audits and energy performance certificates of buildings,
- Technical progress in the profession (materials, equipment, technologies, methodologies, etc.),
- Changes related to regulations in the field of energy efficiency of buildings, changes in European law in this area,

- Development of computer tools for calculating the energy performance of a building,
- The correctness, accuracy and completeness of the issued energy certificates of buildings and prepared reports on regular inspection of heating systems and cooling systems or air conditioning in the building, determined on the basis of supervision and control.

To achieve the above-mentioned goals, the training programme for authorized persons lasting 8 to 16 hours (depending on technological progress in the field of energy efficiency in buildings, changes in building and technical regulations, and the development of computer tools) contains the following subjects:

1. Legislative and regulatory framework for the implementation of energy audits and energy certification of buildings:
 - 1.1. Overview of new directives or amendments to existing directives and other sources of European energy efficiency law,
 - 1.2. Review of new or amendments to existing laws and regulations in the field of energy efficiency in the Republic of Croatia,
2. Distinguishing content in relation to training programs according to previously applicable regulations. The content of this module changes depending on the change of regulations and the mandatory content of the training programme.
3. Experiences from conducted energy audits of buildings,
4. Experience in issuing energy certificates,
5. Experience from the conducted supervision of the work of authorized persons:
 - 5.1. Report on supervision of the work of authorised persons,
 - 5.2. Accuracy and truthfulness of data,
 - 5.3. Ethical issues in work,
6. Innovative solutions to improve energy efficiency and improve the implementation of energy audits and examples of good practices,
 - 6.1. New materials, equipment, technologies and approaches to improve energy efficiency in buildings and their application,
 - 6.2. Examples of good practice and transfer of experience and knowledge from other European countries (optional),
7. Computer tools.

Content of a new voluntary training course in Austria

Quality Austria in cooperation with ARGE-STIBA HOLDING Academy, the Austrian Building Academies (lecturers from the regional building guilds, industry and business) and klimaaktiv (lecturers from the Federal Ministry) offer a voluntary training course, which is called „certified EPC issuer“.

This training course is intended for people who are authorized to issue an energy performance certificate or for people who are involved in this topic in their work.

Content of the course:

- Fundamentals for the calculation of energy performance indicators as an essential basis for the preparation of the energy performance certificate in accordance with EPBD, OIB RL6 (legal requirements for energy efficient building and EPCs), EPC submission act and various state laws
- Basic principles of building physics and building services engineering
- Technical principles and the effects of various measures on energy performance indicators using specific examples
- Implementation of the relevant laws and standards
- Know-how for submission and consultation

This is followed by an examination and certification of the knowledge acquired.

Duration:

Module 1: 2 x 2 days, basic training

Module 2: 1 x 2 days, exam preparation

Module 3: 1 x 1 day, certification exam

Module 4: Knowledge check for external exam candidates

Quality Austria graduates such as environmental system managers, energy officers and/or EPC issuers can claim the points credited to them when they are recognized as internal energy auditors.

The course is voluntary and is targeted to give the certified EPC issuers a competitive advantage, which should increase the demand for the course and thus increase the quality of EPCs.

13 Appendix 3. Description of consultations regarding the training of EPC issuers with national stakeholders

AUSTRIA: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

Identified gaps in training and potential improvements

Insufficient standardization and harmonization of education

One challenge is the lack of standardization of training requirements for energy performance certificate issuers. In Austria, without any specific training concerning the issuance of an EPC can be done by the following trades:

In the following, those groups of tradesmen or self-employed persons are listed who are authorized to issue energy performance certificates.

Tradesmen/Professionals:

- Master builder
- Electrical engineering
- Gas and sanitary engineering
- Heating technology
- Refrigeration and air-conditioning technology
- Ventilation technology
- Master woodworkers
- Engineering offices (consulting engineers), in particular in the following specialist areas are qualified and authorised to issue energy performance certificates:
 - Building physics
 - Electrical engineering
 - Building services engineering (installation, heating and air conditioning)
 - Interior design
 - Mechanical engineering
 - Technical physics
 - Environmental technology
 - Process engineering
- Chimney sweeper: Issuing of EPCs for existing residential buildings except, not for new buildings and alterations to structures requiring a building permit
- Hafner (Someone who installs stoves): Issuing of energy performance certificates for detached and semi-detached houses.

Civil engineers:

- Entitled are civil engineers with relevant authority, such as in particular:
- Architects,
- civil engineers and engineering consultants for
 - Civil engineering
 - Industrial engineering - civil engineering
 - Technical physics
 - Process Engineering
 - Mechanical Engineering
 - Building services engineering

At the moment, there is no obligation to do any kind of special education concerning EPC calculation if you fall into one of the occupational groups.

There are courses about using the EPC calculation software from different service providers, but they are voluntary. So the qualification of EPC issuers is quite inhomogeneous and so is the quality of the EPCs.

Calculating energy efficiency often requires a deep understanding of the structural aspects and energy flows in a building. Experts in building physics may not have high qualifications or expertise in building service equipment and vice versa. So, both trades need a certain level of both fields. The more complex a building is, the more specific and comprehensive has the knowledge to be. The basic education in both trades – or all the trades who are allowed to issue EPCs – has to have a certain technical level to be able to issue accurate EPCs.

Recommendation: A harmonized training concept could ensure that all energy performance certificate issuers have comparable knowledge and skills.

Outdated knowledge

As building science standards, energy efficiency technologies and regulations are constantly evolving, some energy certification professionals may not have the most up-to-date knowledge.

Recommendation: Ongoing training is important to ensure that professionals stay up to date concerning technical progress and they also should be trained in how to calculate new technologies in the EPC software programs. There are offers by the EPC software companies – e.g. how the change in the OIB Guideline 6 (legal requirements for energy efficient building and EPCs) affect the calculation of EPCs. But these trainings are voluntary.

Default values

Another point on the agenda should be the use of default values and the calculation of EPCs:

In different EPC calculation software, no indication of the range, limits and meaning of default values are given. Often these values are kept and may not meet the actual condition of the building. There is no specific training on this and the knowledge about the effect of certain inputs is often missing and thus default values are often chosen inappropriately for the building. There are already default values filled in automatically but information about them is missing

Awareness of the sensitivity of a EPC calculation

Experience of sensitivity is very important – i.e. calculate a building several times or several participants calculate the same building to compare inputs and results afterwards. This increases the sensitivity of a calculation and the awareness for a correct or a realistic data input.

Considering that the results of the EPC are used as a basis for a renovation roadmap, then it is even more important that the inputs are appropriate and realistic.

Limited practical experience

Some energy performance auditors may not have sufficient practical fieldwork experience, which could affect their ability to collect accurate data and provide realistic recommendations.

Recommendation: Regular exchange of experience or mandatory participation in refresher training in connection to the ongoing training for technical progress and regulations (EPC submission act and OIB Guideline 6 – energy saving and heat protection, which is the legal document for meeting the EPBD requirements).

Special knowledge necessary for complex buildings

The diversity of building types requires specific training for EPC providers. Issuing an EPC for single family houses is not as complex as issuing an EPC for specific non-residential buildings. A comprehensive understanding of the different building structures is important in order to produce accurate EPCs. In the future the use of BIM will increase and therefore training in this field is also important.

Collecting accurate data

The quality of the EPC also depends heavily on the accuracy of the incoming data. Gathering precise information on building characteristics, building materials, system technology and occupants' usage habits as well as documentation of the previous renovation measures can be a challenge. End users do not

want to pay a lot for an EPC but gathering precise information often is very time consuming and thus increases the costs for an EPC.

A targeted communication strategy concerning the EPC, emphasising the value, the benefits and the functions of a sound EPC may lead to a better understanding and may overcome the barrier of costs.

Communication skills

The ability to communicate complex technical information clearly to the building users is important. However, there may be gaps in training when it comes to developing effective communication skills.

What is important is, that the EPC issuer receives support in communicating also by getting a list and descriptions of benefits.

Cooperation among professionals

In order to meet all these challenges, continuous training is important to keep up to date with the latest technology and legislation. In addition, the planners of various disciplines during planning a building, such as architects, master builders, engineers, energy consultants etc. should cooperate intensively to ensure a comprehensive and accurate energy performance certificate.

Costs of training courses

Professionals often do not have lots of time available for further education and for smaller companies the costs often may be too high.

Recommendation: Giving financial support for such kind of education to SMEs.

BULGARIA: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

DATE: 09 November 2023

PLACE: Sofia, World Bank office and Zoom

CONSULTATIONS FORMAT: workshop in hybrid format

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (**Implementer of the national building policies; Building norms developer**)

Sustainable Energy Development Agency (**Controlling body for all EPC-related issues**)

Training providers: Technical University – Sofia (**EPC Training provider**)

Ruse University “Angel Kanchev” (**EPC Training provider**)

University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy (**EPC Training provider**)

Thracian University (**EPC training provider**) – online participation

Chamber of the Energy Auditors (Association of **EPC issuers**)

Main conclusions form discussions:**Identified weaknesses in national provisions for training for EPC issuers**

During this part of the discussion, the participants agreed on the following:

The agenda of the current trainings for energy auditors follows the requirements of the ordinance regulating the training, but it is from 2018, and it is advisable to be updated periodically.

Conducting training of the highest quality is extremely important. The current training materials are not good enough, especially in the areas of building physics and construction, and need to be optimized and some of the lectures completely revised.

The training courses held involve too many lectures presenting fundamental science, but the participants in the courses are university graduates and are already familiar with many of the materials during their studies at universities. It is much more important to focus on the practical aspects related to the implementation of energy audits and the certification of buildings. More useful for participants would be to increase the number of practical hours for building energy auditing and certification during the courses. The Chamber of Energy Auditors proposes to make research and propose buildings whose owners would agree to be audited as part of the training courses.

Another important aspect that is currently missing is the conduction of trainings of trainers. Such training can make the learning process much more efficient.

The participants also discussed the most used building energy modelling (EESCalc) software and agreed that improvements need to be made, both in terms of input and processing of primary data, and in terms of automating the issuance of EPCs as a result of the work with the software.

Potential improvements in national EPC training process

Kamen Simeonov from EnEffect, representative of the crossCert project, presented several proposals for improvements in the training program for energy auditors. Some of the proposed changes include adding new lectures, as well as optimizing the current training materials. Other important proposals are to divide the full list of lectures into modules and to regulate the number of hours for each module instead of each lecture, as it is now in the ordinance. The number of hours may be different for training participants who have different professional profiles. Another suggestion is to consider including the training in the regular curriculum of universities. The introduction of practical exercises on measurements was proposed and it was stressed that the practical part of the training should cover the whole process of the energy audit, starting from the visit to the building and the collection of initial data.

The participants in the discussion agreed with the proposals. The representatives of the universities expressed their support for the introduction of the training in the regular curriculum of the universities, the division of the program into modules for different professionals, as well as for the introduction of more practical exercises into the agenda. On the other hand, they stressed that they are obliged to follow the requirements of the current ordinance regulating the trainings. The Chamber of Energy Auditors also supported the introduction of separate modules for different specialists and the addition of practical exercises.

Upgrading and updating of the EESCalc software was also discussed. The comments included improving the functionalities, presentation of final calculated results, adding new input and output data and automatic document generation. If updated as proposed, the software will cover most of the steps in the energy audit process and most of the required official documents, including EPC, will be generated automatically. The representative from the University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy noted that the climate data used to calculate the energy performance of buildings is too old and needs to be updated. The data do not take into account climate change and air temperature rise.

DENMARK: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

DATE: 15 May 2024

Summary of consultations made through events and bilateral dialogues (EPC issuers, Danish Energy Authority, Central Denmark Region, ECNet)

Main conclusions:

More focus on the past EPC process

Overall, the EPC is increasingly recognized as an important component of the energy renovation process. Therefore, it is crucial to establish a clear link between the EPC report and the subsequent implementation process, while considering the specific requirements of each stage. This can a.o. include a more focused training of assessor on these points.

- Enhance the focus on providing actionable recommendations and facilitating end-users in taking the necessary steps post-assessment.
- Emphasize how EPCs can be used for securing financing options (mandatory in Denmark), linking energy performance improvements with financial incentives.
- Encourage follow-up actions with buyers to ensure the implementation of EPC recommendations (change in EPC process)

Effective Communication Skills

Further develop assessors' ability to communicate EPC report aspects clearly and explain their utility to end-users, including potential cost savings.

This may have to be supplemented by an even better and more user-friendly design of the EPC.

More focus on deep renovation

Deep renovation issues are included in the Danish training, but there needs to be further guidelines and training on how to handle this in the EPC context, and in relation to the ongoing recast of EU Directives where deep renovation is in focus.

Hands-On Training and Practical Experience:

Reintroduce Mentorship Programs that pair trainees with experienced EPC issuers for mentorship and on-the-job training to enhance practical learning.

This may be complemented with practical workshops and on-site training sessions where trainees can gain hands-on experience in conducting energy assessments and using relevant tools and software.

Further peer review systems where EPC reports are evaluated by other professionals may ensure enhanced quality and consistency.

Strengthen Legal and Regulatory Knowledge:

Enhance training on legal aspects, including contract design and the consultant's responsibilities, to ensure assessors are well-versed in the regulatory framework and ISO 9001 certification requirements.

Further it is important to regularly revise and update training materials to reflect any changes in EU Directives and national regulations, ensuring assessors remain well-informed and compliant with current laws.

This also involves aspect in relation to the current digitalization process in Denmark.

Deepen Methodological Understanding

Strengthen the training programs to ensure a common and thorough understanding of the EPC methodology, focusing on reducing errors and increasing the overall quality of the assessments.

GREECE: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

DATE: 20 February 2024

PLACE: Zoom

CONSULTATIONS FORMAT: workshop in online format

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

Ministry of Energy and Environment, Secretary of issuers and auditors (**Controlling body for all EPC-related issues**)

Technical Chamber of Greece (Association of **EPC issuers** , **EPC Training provider**)

Auditors

Introduction

The CrossCert project, Work Package 5 and Task 5.3 were briefly presented, in order to explain to the participants, the framework of the workshop. The differences in training, legislation among CrossCert's countries were also presented.

Identified problems from the stakeholder's point of view

During a period of the EPC's implementation, training provided to energy inspector candidates and the relevant exams, was obligatory but when it became not obligatory the level of knowledge of the accessors dropped down and as a result the quality of EPCs declined significantly. The issuing of an EPC became routine work usually targeting in achieving the necessary energy class for the building. The part of the recommendations for the energy upgrade in the EPC, is not elaborated essentially but rather typically, it is perceived to not consist of an important part of the EPC. Building owners from their side do not understand the value of an EPC and do not press for their good quality. For that the Technical Chamber of Greece and other institutions could support with awareness campaigns.

As far as background training is concerned, some academic faculties, for example mechanical engineers, guarantee a level of relative knowledge, while others do not and thus require additional and specialised training. Many new engineers are asking for information and training.

There is a lack of understanding of the legislation and regulations relevant to the EPCs, by the energy inspectors themselves, as well as other stakeholders (e.g. notaries who are required to attach the EPC to contracts). Differences in notions and procedures between EPC regulations and general building and tax legislation create a lot of confusion for everyone involved.

The Controlling Body at the Ministry of Energy and Environments has identified serious mistakes made by EPC issuers during random checks. There is a serious lack of knowledge even regarding legislation. Besides, software packages do not perform adequate error checking.

Main takeaways

There is a great need for training to increase the quality of EPCs. The courses should include the presentation and secure an understanding of the existing regulatory framework as well as the software. Most of the issuers do not have a satisfactory understanding of how the software properly works.

Training should be provided and not just once but regularly.

Training should include:

- Information on electromechanical systems and technical equipment specifications to educate auditors on the latest developments in equipment
- Updates on additional requirements for buildings (SRI, human behaviour, real consumption etc.).
- Legislation and regulations relevant to EPCs, as well as their relationships with general building legislation / regulations
- EPCs software and the TOTEE (Technical Instructions of the Technical Chamber of Greece).
- Theoretical knowledge but also on site and hands on training.
- Exams every 3-5 years

It was suggested that alongside the formal training, awareness campaigns or specialized informational activities should be targeted at the general public as well as stakeholders (e.g. notaries, accountants) and civil servants involved with EPCs. The need for regularly updated material (e.g. FAQs, wiki), issued by the Ministry of Energy and / or the Technical Chamber of Greece, clarifying details for inspectors and other stakeholders.

A separate work environment for self-training could be provided within the EPCs Registry for energy inspectors to use, for experimenting and trying out their work before uploading their EPCs to the 'formal' Registry.

Finally, it was also proposed that EPCs should be issued by a team of energy inspectors with different profiles, each one specialized to a sector, who could complement each other, especially when it comes to large and complex buildings.

CROATIA: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

DATE: 15 November 2023

PLACE: Zagreb, EKONERG premises

CONSULTATIONS FORMAT: workshop in physical format

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets (**Implementer of the national building policies**)

North-West Croatia Energy and Climate Agency (**Energy and Climate agency/EPC issuers**)

Hrvoje Požar Energy Institute (**EPC Training provider**)

State Agency for Legal Traffic and Real Estate Brokerage (**National body**)

EKONERG (**covers the entire service cycle from an idea of building a facility, preparing the construction to managing construction, maintenance and asset management and making environmental impact assessments**)

Energy auditors and designers.

Main conclusions from discussions:

Identified challenges in national provisions for training for EPC issuers

TIMEPAC project, via TIMEPAC Academy, provides training and resources tailored specifically for professionals engaged in building assessment and certification. The platform is dedicated to equipping individuals with the essential knowledge and skills needed to transition from one-time certifications to comprehensive assessments of building performance throughout its entire lifespan. To enable this, the existing training schemes should be investigated in order to provide best basis for future trainings focussed on new indicators (e.g. SRI, comfort) and certification schemes.

As defined in the Ordinance on persons authorized for energy certification, energy audit of the building and regular inspection of heating and cooling systems or air conditioning systems in the building, the training program is mandatory once every two years attended by authorized natural persons, and appointed as well as other employed persons, who carry out energy certification, energy audit of the building and regular inspection of heating and cooling systems or air conditioning in the building, in authorized legal entities. In case of non-fulfilment of this obligation, work in the electronic system for issuing energy certificates is automatically disabled, starting from January 1, 2023.

The issuance of energy certificates began in 2010/2011 for non-residential buildings larger than 1000 m² with the energy class based on $Q_{h,nd}$. The control of energy certificates began in 2014, with the average positive rating of the certificate being approximately 50%.

The process of energy certification becomes more demanding starting with 1.10.2017, when two energy classes for the same building are introduced – $Q_{h,nd}$ and E_{prim} . In doing so, the mandatory application of an electronic system for issuing an energy certificate, new tools for calculation, a new methodology and an Algorithm are introduced. At the same time, the market in Croatia is recovering, architects are turning to their basic business and the number of certifications of certifiers is falling.

The agenda of the current trainings for energy auditors follows the new requirements. Nevertheless, energy audits and certification become demanding especially for buildings undergoing energy renovation or some other forms of support:

- Mandatory participation of all three professions in the calculation up to E_{prim} (mechanical ventilation),
- In the tenders, savings verification is requested, certificate data for the starting state are not available,

- All savings measures should be carried out through building physics,
- More accurate data on savings are being sought, the calculation of "physics" is becoming more extensive (the complexity of thermomechanical systems requires zoning of the building).

Potential improvements in national EPC training process

Potential improvements were discussed in the framework of new challenges and new EU legislative framework (newest EPBD recast).

Due to mandatory participation of all three professions, as well as many different stakeholders involved in the process of certification and later use of EPCs for savings verifications, stakeholders underscored the potential of Building Information Modelling (BIM) in data collection and validation, recognizing its value. However, challenges remain, including sporadic use in Croatia and concerns over implementation costs. The introduction of new indicators, such as the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), was welcomed as an enhancement to energy building performance presentation. The importance of clear definitions and procedures (in terms of skills, datasets, and software) and the manifestation of new indicators was highlighted by all participants.

Particular attention was given to the need for actual operational data on savings, acknowledging the increasing influence of occupants and users in the energy certification process. Stakeholders highlighted the importance of digitalization, advocating for accessibility to the energy model of the building for professionals and energy auditors. The interoperability of datasets emerged as a crucial aspect requiring dedicated efforts.

For the Renovation Wave to happen there need to be clear benefits for building users. The energy certification process could become more cost-effective for clients by leveraging previous information and building on existing datasets. Clear definitions and procedures for new indicators were identified as vital components for successful implementation.

The information gathered in this workshop seek to lay the foundations of positive change in Croatia's energy certification landscape and to expand existing trainings in accordance with the news in up-coming legislation. These collaborative efforts will pave the way for a more efficient, transparent, and accessible process, empowering building experts and ensuring a sustainable future through advancements in energy certification.

POLAND: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

DATE: -

PLACE: Warsaw, Microsoft Teams

CONSULTATIONS FORMAT: round-about with Ministry during national level events, various workshops during projects, "Meeting with the expert" – KAPE's webinar series on energy transition

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

Energy Agencies (**Advisory body for EPCs**)

Ministry of Economic Development and Technology (**Controlling body for all EPC-related issues**)

Association of Energy Auditors (**Association of EPC issuers**)

Auditors (**EPC issuers**)

Introduction

The CrossCert project, Work Package 5 and Task 5.3 were briefly presented, in order to explain to the participants, the framework of the workshop. The differences in training and legislation among CrossCert's countries were also presented.

Identified problems from the stakeholder's point of view

To be authorized to create EPCs, one must be included in the list of authorized, which is part of the central register of energy performance of buildings. To be included in the list, you must meet the following requirements:

- have full legal capacity
- not be sentenced by a final judgment for a crime against property,
- credibility of documents, economic turnover, dealing in money and securities, or a fiscal crime
- have a construction license

or

have completed:

- higher education studies leading to the award of the professional title of engineer, architect engineer, landscape architect engineer, fire engineer, master's degree in architecture, master's degree in landscape architecture, master's degree in fire engineering, or master's degree in engineering or
- higher education other than those listed above and postgraduate studies, the program of which takes into account issues related to energy performance of buildings, performance of energy audits of buildings, energy-efficient construction and renewable energy sources.

Currently, there are no auditor retraining courses conducted in Poland, nor is there any exam to confirm auditors' knowledge.

The main problems are:

- low quality of EPCs, mainly due to the lack of control by the Ministry, the lack of need for an on-site visit by the auditor
- outdated knowledge of auditors - those who gained registration 10 years ago do not need to update their knowledge
- small number of auditors, regardless of their level of knowledge
- lack of recommendations
- an underdeveloped EPC database

Main takeaways

In conversations, the issue of poor quality EPCs and lack of value for owners is often raised due to issuers' lack of knowledge about building renovation. EPCs at the moment are often seen as an unpleasant chore rather than a document that can help renovate a building.

The Ministry has initiated EPC inspections, and some auditors have been removed from the Ministry's roster because the quality of the documents was poor.

However, there is still a lack of inspection of auditors before they are listed in the database, experts and associations see the need for a certification system for auditors, where it would be necessary to pass exams on building knowledge. One temporary solution is a list of recommended auditors created by the Association of Energy Auditors, where auditors are tested on their knowledge. However, the association is not in a position to audit all those on the register and building owners do not always know of the existence of such an association and rely on the Ministry's database or, even worse, the first results on an Internet search engine.

The Ministry believes that studies should be sufficient to form EPCs but does not rule out the introduction of courses or additional requirements after the EPBD introduces Renovation Passports and Building Logs. The introduction of an exam on building renovation knowledge is also under consideration.

Another obstacle to creating a course for auditors is the lack of official software for calculating EPCs, which would require showing multiple options for creating EPCs.

The training should include:

- Energy efficiency in construction - EU directives, the Thermal Modernization Law, implementing regulations, basic information
- Issues of building physics
- Planning of building thermomodernization
- EPCs software
- Calculation examples

In addition, each auditor should update his knowledge and pass a knowledge exam every 5 years.

SLOVENIA: SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS ON TRAINING FOR EPC ISSUERS

Researchers involved: Domen Bančič, Jure Vetršek & Eva Zavrl (IRI UL)

Stakeholder organizations represented¹¹ and their role in buildings energy performance certification process:

1. MOPE - Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy, Sector for energy use **(EPC system developer and implementor)**
2. ZRMK - Building and Civil Engineering Institute, The Centre for Indoor Environment, Building Physics and Energy **(one of two EPC Training providers in Slovenia)**
3. IJS CEU - The Jožef Stefan Institute Energy Efficiency Centre **(research institution specializing on EPC related topics)**
4. LEST - Laboratory of Energy Policy, Faculty of electrical engineering, University of Ljubljana **(research institute specializing on energy related topics)**
5. Assistant at the faculty of Mechanical Engineering UL **(Participant in the EPC training – year 2023)**
6. Energy auditor and energy manager at UL **(Participant in the EPC training – year 2014)**
7. Certified EPC assessor **(participant in the EPC training – year 2013)**

GENERAL NOTES

Training content characterization

Education of EPC assessors is indeed very important:

- It is the key starting point for the national building certification system (the EPC System) to function.
- It is the way for experts to acquire knowledge, stay up to date, and gain the necessary experience to provide quality assessment service in the fast-changing landscape of energy in buildings.
- It is the precondition for sustaining the quality of the EPC System as well as advancing this field of expertise to the next level.

The training of EPC assessors & issuers¹² in Slovenia has changed significantly since its introduction in years 2013/14 to today (MAR 2024):

- The numbers of course participants are significantly smaller - in the early years even up to 50 participants per class, now less than 10 per class), as for now, the total number of approximately 400 are trained which by some accounts is enough for the Slovenian market.
- The number of presential hours is significantly lesser as well – in the past the course was designed as an intensive course of 3 to 4 days of up to 6 presential hours per day (28 h in total), then exams. Today there is typically one day – 6 hours – of introductory presential course, then participants have access to online materials and take the exam when they are prepared. The training provider¹³ provides support to the candidates when needed (typically via call or email, answering specific questions by the candidates).

¹¹ The views expressed by the interviewees are their own and might not represent the official view of the institution they represent.

¹² In Slovenia, EPC assessors and EPC issuers are not necessarily one and the same person or entity and can in theory function independently. That said, in practice this often is the same person or institution.

¹³ Up to date, we have two institutions in Slovenia authorized by the responsible public body (MOPE) for executing the training for EPC assessors – ZRMK (Building and Civil Engineering Institute) and ZAPS (Chamber of Architecture and Spatial Planning of Slovenia).

- The structure of participants changed noticeably through time as well, depending on the requirements that are associated with EPCs. In the early years the primary motivation was economical – many participants were energy advisors who are required to get certified in order to continue working in their job and other professionals (self-employed architects or engineers or representative of companies) who hoped to enrich the portfolio of services they offer in the construction sector. Nowadays training participants and candidates are attending primarily to enhance their knowledge and consolidate their professional profile as an expert in a specific field.
- The content has developed as well. There are constant changes in technology and policy and the training needs to evolve accordingly.

The course for certified EPC assessors in Slovenia today consists of:

- The candidates apply for the training with the responsible training provider and pay the training participation fee (also the fee for the exam if they wish to take the exam; these are two separate things). Some participate exclusively to gain knowledge, not the certificate.
- An introductory presential class (approximately 6 h long) dedicated to presentation of the course structure, requirements for taking the exam, functioning of the online classroom¹⁴ and other relevant meta-information. The course is also dedicated to the most relevant updates on the EPBD transposition (laws and regulation updates) and the exchange of relevant experience between the course participants, although to a lesser extent than in the past (the exchange of experiences now takes place on dedicated online forums and at periodic training for already certified EPCs) ().
- An online classroom with recorded video presentations and study materials on key topics, Q&A and a forum for EPC-related discussions.
- Support and/or consultations for candidates via telephone or email provided by the training provider.
- The exam, which consists of (1) a written test (the theory) and (2) an oral exam (defence) of the candidate's EPCs (both the calculated and a measured one) produced exclusively for the purpose of the exam (the practical part).
- Regarding the balance between theory and practice, the representative of training providers claimed that based on their analysis of time required to approach the exam, the participants invest a comparable amount of time to both theory and practice. In contrast, based experiences reported by course participants, the content of the training¹⁵ is almost exclusively theoretical, focusing on the following key aspects:
 - The categorization and specifications of systems and building physics that need to be understood by the assessor/issuer to successfully issue an EPC.
 - Laws and regulations associated with the EPCs;
 - The procedures and practices that need to be followed by the assessor to issue an EPC successfully;
 - The discrepancy in perceptions noted above is most likely due to how we consider the time required for producing the two EPCs needed to approach the exam, more specifically, if we consider this as part of the training or not (the candidates are required to produce the EPCs on their own but are welcome to ask the training provider for advice and support). Either way, all stakeholders agree that both theory and practice are crucial parts of the training. The fact is that the training course requires candidates to issue one measured and one calculated EPC. From the training provider's standpoint, this work is considered as the practical part of the course and is also evaluated as part of the exam.
- The training content, particularly the part on technical expertise, is good quality and very high level, as virtually all interviewees reported. This is also reflected in the fact that many candidates have to repeat the certification exam once or twice before they pass. What is arguably missing and could be improved are customer-centred aspects (communication & customer support).

¹⁴ <https://trajnostnagrada.si/ucilnica/>

¹⁵ <http://www.ee.fs.uni-lj.si/ZAPS-LOTZ/gradivo.html>

Training participants characterization

- The vast majority of those who participate in the EPC training course in Slovenia come from a technical background, as this is also a legal requirement¹⁶ for those who wish to take the exam. However, there is also a significant number of training participants from both technical and non-technical background that take the course only to enhance their knowledge in the field, without the intention of taking the exam (inspectors, professionals working in the energy sector, public sector and municipal workers etc.).
- A rough estimate is that from those that take the exam, around 40% are mechanical engineers, 30% are civil engineers, around 15% are architects and another 15% are other technical professions. Historically the reason for keeping this job open to a wider range of technical professions is to regulate the market – if it would be limited to one specific profile (e.g. mechanical engineers who are certified by a chamber of engineers) the market price of EPC assessment would likely be very high due to the more limited number of professionals eligible to perform this job.
- As noted earlier, the structure of participant groups changes over time, but the vast majority takes the course as part of their professional development related to their job.
- The motives for participants to take the course are largely pragmatic:
 - In some cases, it is a requirement by participant's employer as it is associated with a specific requirement or a business opportunity for the company/employer.
 - In some cases, it might be seen as a career development opportunity (continuous professional development) – for young professionals especially.
 - Some people and companies see it primarily as a personal business opportunity (recent years less due to low prices of EPCs and the saturation of the market with certified assessors offering the service).
- Participant satisfaction with the training is generally positive:
 - Most candidates that take the course also pass the exam, though many must repeat it two or three times. That said, there are also course participants who never take the exam.
 - Participants are happy with the current length and structure of the course, an observation reported by both the training provider and the participants interviewed. Candidates have explicitly appreciated the possibility to study for the exam at their own pace (using the online classroom) as most of them study on top of their full-time jobs.

Training system characterization

- The training providers are chosen based on criteria defined by the public tender¹⁷ issued by the Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy (MOPE). The individuals employed by one of the two official training providers in Slovenia¹⁸ who execute the training are highly educated and trained professionals in their field of expertise. They attend relevant training courses and educate themselves according to their own judgement. There are no unified requirements for qualification of the training providers and there is no official training program for the “training of trainers”. They are given the mandate to execute the course based on the outcome of the tender.
- The training content is periodically updated according to:
 - Changes in laws and regulations;
 - Changes to the EPC register (issuing procedure).
- As reported by the training provider, supplementary training for already certified EPC assessors is periodically organized by the responsible legislative body (in our case MOPE) as it is required by state

¹⁶ <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAVI3413>

¹⁷ <https://www.energetika-portal.si/javne-objave/arhiv-energetika/javni-razpisi/r/javni-razpis-za-izbiro-izvajalca-usposabljanja-in-preizkusa-znanja-za-neodvisne-strokovnja-1259/>

¹⁸ <https://energetskaizkaznica.si/usposabljanje/#izkaznica> and <http://www.ee.fs.uni-lj.si/ZAPS-LOTZ/index.html>

regulation and provided periodically (in principle every 5 years). Participation at these events is a condition for the extension of the license. Topical issues addressed on those trainings are:

- Changes in legislation,
- Supervisory findings,
- Other professional issues.

While the representatives of the legislative body (MOPE) and the training provider (ZRMK) were clear on the point, that periodic upskilling for already certified EPC assessors is obligatory, reports and opinions expressed by our interviewees were incoherent with this statement, noting that this rule is not enforced and that the decision to attend the supplementary training is left completely to the assessor's judgement. According to the representative of the legislative body, this is a false assumption as they have just recently revoked licenses to a number of EPC assessors due to their failure to attend the periodic upskilling event.

- The active EPC assessor noted that the training provider is very professional and always willing to support assessors with their work and professional challenges.

Quality control

Legal consequences for poor assessment practice are defined by state regulation¹⁹. The professional control protocol is defined by the Ministry of infrastructure and is comparable in scope to other countries in the EU:

- The first step is professional supervision.
- In case of inaccuracies or faults, the first reminder is issued to the EPC issuer/assessor.
- In case of repeated errors, the license is revoked. Professional control over the correctness of an individual EPCs can also be initiated by an inspector based on a report (these cases are not many, but they do exist).

The people-centered aspects in the training

Viewpoints reported by the interviewees on how much the training course addresses the "people-centred" or "the human aspects," such as the topic of working with clients (the assessment as a service, engagement with clients, promotion of EPCs and their purpose, professional communication, motivation for building retrofits etc.), are somewhat contradictory:

- Some interviewees noted that training materials offer limited or virtually no theoretical or practical content related to the practice of customer service or site visit/inspection. Similarly deficient, they claimed, is content addressing the declared purpose of EPCs (what the global aim of EPCs is, how it is supposed to affect the clients/homeowner and the market). They reported limited content related to communication and/or work with customers, as well as limited content related to the use of EPCs once they are issued.
- In contrast, the representative of the training provider and the active certified assessor stated that these topics are well addressed during the course and that there is plenty of discussion on the topic both during the course and in the periodic upskilling courses.
- An EPC expert and researcher claimed that for most participants the people-centred skills should be promoted as the main added value of the course. The majority of course participants should be well acquainted with the technical part of the knowledge shared on the course, they claimed, while the people-centered aspects, which are essential for the EPC system to generate real impact, are largely a novelty for course participants. This opinion was shared by several consultation participants, expressing an opinion that quality of the EPC certification service would increase and with it the willingness of homeowners to pursue building renovations measures.
- The representative of the legislative body (MOPE) noted that EPC assessors were required from the very beginning to be "an interdisciplinary profile" and recognized that with time they continuously need to pursue mastery of new skills and qualifications on top of their baseline knowledge. In

¹⁹ Articles 8–20: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAV13413>

addition, they noted that EPCs are only a small part in pursuit of optimization of energy performance of the building stock, implying that such people-centred contents should be associated with other activities and initiatives, and not specifically required from the EPC assessors as such.

- The active EPC assessor also noted that work with clients in practice can be a very frustrating and futile endeavour. Often there can be a significant lack of interest on the client's side, despite assessor's best intentions to communicate specific aspects of the value of EPCs while the assessment and certification service is taking place. This is common in cases when EPCs are needed for property sales and even more so with larger institutions, where the task of ordering an EPC is often delegated to an office worker who typically knows and cares very little about the building's energy performance. In such cases motivation and interest on the client's side go little further than learning about the cost of the service and when the EPC will be issued before the task is finalized and reported to the superiors.
- Despite contrast and discrepancy in the outlined viewpoints, all stakeholders agree working with clients is a very important aspect and that candidates for EPC assessor's certification need to be properly trained in this regard. Although they don't need to be expected to persuade or sell anything to their clients during the course of the service, at the very least that the assessors should act as active ambassadors of the EPC system and the purpose associated with it (optimization of energy use in buildings, holistic building renovations aiming towards near-zero standard, building renovations for health, safety, sustainability, resiliency etc.).

Representative of the training provider stated that technical issues are *not* the main challenges of the Slovenian EPC System, as the initial technical issues have been largely resolved by now. The existing EPC System and specifically the EPC assessors training faces challenges in the following points:

- Due to quickly changing policy & regulation, the candidates often approach the exam having studied outdated policy & regulation.
- The existing issuers often have a negative response to change to their way/system of working if it challenges their existing level of knowledge and competence. As the system/method changes and becomes more complex (e.g. from month to hourly calculational methods), the amount of work and training required to stay certified is growing. Many EPC professionals are not willing or sufficiently motivated to learn and improve their skills, especially because they feel the evolution of the method is unnecessarily complex for their understanding of the purpose of the EPC system. On the long run, this could have a negative impact on the existing pool of certifiers and quality. To a degree, this also implies current and future candidates for certification and might present a challenge for the system in the future (currently the market is stable and the system functions).
- The point above is related to the **challenge of the EPC market price** – more complexity of the system and the calculation method implies more workload and higher costs. If we add on the idea of enhanced interaction with clients, this issue becomes even more severe. One interviewee suggested that there should be subsidies available to finance production of quality EPCs, since good quality EPCs should be a strategic interest of the government for advance spatial planning, systematic infrastructural investment planning, planning for long-term resilience of the construction market (subsidized building renovation as a buffer in case of decreased market demand for new construction), national reporting on climate neutrality goals, etc.
- The limited role of EPCs in context of the real estate market:
 - The representative of the official training provider claimed that EPCs are intentionally marginalized by the key market stakeholders in Slovenia, which has a negative impact on the system's purpose & goals.
 - The representative of MOPE noted that a study they performed with the Surveying and Mapping Authority of the Republic of Slovenia showed EPCs fail to have a significant impact on the real estate market in Slovenia, as primary factor is location but on 3rd-5th place there is energy.

- The representation of the EPC indicators for the properties being sold is still not properly enforced in Slovenia – it is required by law²⁰ but not (yet) widely enforced with penalties.
- The issue of purpose – in case of buying/selling property, the EPC assessment service is paid by the seller, who perceives the purpose of the EPC as a condition to sell the building, and not to renovate it. The EPC is thus supposed to be “used” by the buyer, who can in fact become the actual owner of the property quite a long time after the EPC is produced (by then it can become irrelevant), or he wants to adapt the investment to his needs, wishes and, above all, his financial capabilities. In this case, he needs a specific renovation and financing plan tailored to his needs, which is more than what the current EPCs provide.
- The recommended measures included in the EPCs are to be developed into a building renovation passport– there is still no clarity on how to do this in relation to the existing EPC system.

It is noteworthy that two interviewees, high-ranking EPC experts, noted that the main problem with the EPC system in Slovenia is not that EPCs would be of lesser or greater quality, but that we are not achieving the impact that would realize the purpose of the EPCs to a satisfactory degree.

- An EPC expert said "it's not even the point that the EPC is of better or worse quality. We're forgetting the story of why we have and need the EPC in the first place. The problem is that there is no renovation of buildings."
- The representative of the training provider stated that “the calculation method is not the biggest problem and the same goes for the quality of the certifier’s work,” and added that the blanket claim that there is "something wrong" with EPCs is often not substantiated by facts.

To the point above, there are bigger issues that limit the impact of the system which the continuous debate about the appropriateness of the calculation methodology or the quality control of produced EPCs cannot eliminate:

- The EPC System needs to increase its reputation (public image).
- The legislator should insist on certain elements of the quality of the EPC scheme operation beyond the technical quality of EPCs:
 - We need consistency in real-estate advertising, sanctioning advertisements noting “EPC in the process of issuing”
 - We need to prevent promotion of assessment service that offers "EPC assessment without a site visit" (this is no longer allowed anyway, but it is still common to find this).
- We need to prevent negative publicity, such as articles by real estate agents and opportunistic experts who criticize EPCs while they themselves ruin the system by offering poor services (e.g. assessment without the site visit).
- The EPCs can be good enough for the experts, but for final users they are still not valuable enough. They need to be simplified, provide a financial estimation of suggested measures, and linked to funding opportunities or others meaningful services that will render them useful in the eyes of the general public. Non-financial benefits, such as health and safety, should be stressed more also by the EPC products and services.
- Research indicates that the existing EPC system in Slovenia has little impact on the real-estate market. To change this, communication should stress the aspect of cost-benefits associated with better energy performance rating. Simple models have already been developed that could be meaningfully integrated in the current system for use by EPC assessors or other service providers that operate with EPCs as data sources (real-estate agents, retrofitting companies, banks etc.).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the stakeholder consultations and own expertise, we defined the following recommendations:

- **Enhance the practical component of the training.** Participants in the training noted that there is much more attention dedicated to theory than to practice, and specifically that there is no practice

²⁰ <https://www.energetika-portal.si/podrocja/energetika/energetske-izkaznice-stavb/za-drzavljan/>

regarding working with customers. Although this contrasts with the view of a training provider, this suggested practice is an area where improvements could be made in the existing training for certified EPC assessors in Slovenia.

- **Re-design the training to enhance a consensus within the expert community that EPCs are not a goal in themselves but an important part for a more sustainable future (e.g. the first step to near zero energy buildings).** In other words, while the quality and accuracy of certification is important, the purpose of why we have the system in place is more important and that is the area in which real focus should be.
- **Enhance education content that deals with customer service aspects.** Build clear acknowledgement of the declared principal purpose of the certification service within the candidates – to boost decision making for investments into building energy efficiency and influence more efficient energy use in buildings.
- **Involve experts from a variety of educational backgrounds** into the process of designing the training or include them as lecturers to cover fields such as customer service & communication, real-estate market dynamics, bank loans and subsidies for building renovations, social justice & responsibility etc.
- **Frame the education framework as a continuously evolving field of expertise.** Changes to the legislation and the EPC Systems (including the calculation method and/or the software used) are constant. The education framework for training of EPC professionals must accommodate this by default, and this should also be clearly communicated to the candidates with an ambition to become certified EPC assessors.
- **Develop new business models that integrate EPC assessments with other services and opportunities for customers.** Combine EPC assessment with other activities and services, such as subsidy applications for building renovations, retrofitting, or services for improvement of Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ). Target (or create) audiences who will recognize the value in the EPC products and services, which is the basis for the realization of the declared purpose of the EPCs. This is necessary also because of the cost of work to issue EPC, which in Slovenia is currently too low for many trained professionals to find it viable to spend time working on EPC assessments.
- **Offer an EPC interpretation service.** In relation to the point above, there is a clear need for expert interpretation of EPCs and guidance to its meaningful use. To decouple this responsibility from the existing EPC system, given the difficulties associated with costs, an associated entity (e.g. in context of One Stop Shops) could take large part of the responsibility to manage aspects associated with people-centred aspects of the system. This could include everything from promotion of EPCs to arranging the assessment and finally guiding clients (homeowners) and other EPC users (e.g. buyers or renters of the property) towards beneficial EPC use-scenarios that would be the best match for their specific profile (needs and wants). This profile would also benefit from training but specifically training on people-centred aspects of the service and how to use the EPCs beneficially.
- **Design the training service for certification of EPC assessors** with attention to the following points:
 - The purpose of education is to empower professionals with the most recent knowledge and skills required for top quality performance in the field of EPBD and energy certification of buildings. In addition, they can extend their expertise to areas such as IEQ and smart buildings and expand the range of skills and services they offer.
 - Education needs to be fragmented, designed as micro-credits or modules that can easily be mastered and integrated in the ongoing practice of work. It should also be rated from a more basic to advanced level, to indicate the level of complexity it implies.
 - The topics/areas covered by trainings also have to be meaningfully related between each other, focusing on how assessors can optimize their professional practice and enhance the value of EPCs for their customers.
 - The professionals involved in the system need to understand that learning to be an EPC professional is an ongoing rather than a finite process.

SPAIN: STAKEHOLDERS CURRENT VISION OF EPC ISSUERS TRAINING

Current Context:

As it has been expressed on different crossCert's reports, the Spanish EPC issuing procedure vaguely describes the energy assessor's educational background requirements (as in Spain there is nothing such as qualificative trainings), which widely amplifies the scope of the assessors entitled to issue EPCs.

Spanish EPC assessment procedures evolution:

- RD 47/2007 – Basic procedure for new buildings energy efficiency certification.
- RD 235/2013 – Basic procedure for buildings energy efficiency certification.
- RD 390/2021 – Basic procedure for buildings energy efficiency certification.

When approved in 2013 the regulation on Energy Performance Certification of Buildings Procedure, it was established that the Ministry of Industry would determine the professional qualifications requirements to subscribe EPCs and the accreditation channels (4th additional provision). It had to be considered the qualification, complementary education, experience, and the complexity of the certification process.

After that, the same Ministry published an informative clarification document on the mentioned regulation (RD 235/2013), where it was confirmed that an EPC issuer would be any technician holding any degree, and/or qualificative profession for building projects development or building construction management, or for technical thermal systems projects development, according to Spanish Building law 38/1999.

Therefore, the Ministry of Industry published in November 2013 that, aside architects and technical architects, competent technicians could be:

- Aeronautic engineer/ technical engineer
- Agronomist engineer/ technical engineer
- Roads, canals, and ports engineer/ technical engineer
- Industrial engineer/ technical engineer
- Mines engineer/ technical engineer
- Mount engineer/ technical engineer
- Naval engineer/ technical engineer
- Telecommunications engineer/ technical engineer
- Chemical engineer (as it is an equivalent certified diploma as Industrial Chemical engineer)

It can be said that there is a common discomfort around this topic. As the list of professionals published shows, the number of assessors can be widely extended even to non-related degrees.

After a while, the legislation concerning the energy certification of buildings was amended by RD 390/2021. This document, in its 6th final provision, proposed the revision of the "competent technician" definition, establishing a period of eighteen months as of June 2021 for the adaptation of this figure of the competent technician to a model based on the knowledge and professional qualifications necessary for the preparation of energy performance certificates. However, three years later, this adaptation has not taken place.

Nevertheless, the process of modifying that last RD 390/2021 is currently in progress. Some recommendations have been expressed by the Spanish National Market and Competence Commission (CNMC) through the report on the Royal Decree Project to modify RD 390/2021, which approves the Basic Procedure for Energy Performance Certification of Buildings (IPN/CNMC/052/22). It has been proposed to delete the current articles of the RD 390/2021 on the matter and substitute them for a new article that establishes the new requirements for issuing EPCs, rather than listing qualified professionals.

The CNMC has expressed a critical appraisal of the definition of the current regulatory framework for accessing the issuing of EPCs:

"The current definition of competent technician has been described by the CNMC, as well as by several associations and professional organisations in the sector, as an excessive and inadequate barrier to market entry. It has also been shown that the current requirement, despite being a barrier for the access to the EPC market, does not comply with the objectives of assuring the quality of the Spanish EPCs."

Generally, this organisation supports the renovation of the current list of professionals (activity reservation) and the modification of the definition of competent technician. In that sense, it has been promoted a definition of qualified professionals based on knowledge/aptitude scenarios, rather than a degree-based definition as existing.

Discussion rounds:

This report is not a summary of an event, but desk research on past interventions of different Spanish stakeholders from two national events where EREN has participated. Currently, the Spanish EPC sector has proposed different methods to implement an EPC training methodology to increase the effectiveness and quality of the tool, which still have some robustness lacks derived from the criteria to select the qualified EPC assessor (among other factors).

FIRST EVENT: QualDeEPC 2nd national workshop. Information and discussion. The green book of good practices for the evaluation and use of EPCs.

DATE: 20-21 January 2021

PLACE: Spanish Confederation of Business Organisations (CEOE), Madrid

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

Ministry for Ecological Transition (MITECO) – **Energy National Policies (amongst other things).**

Ministry for Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda (MITMA) – **Dwellings, Buildings and Urbanism Policies (amongst other things).**

Galician Energy Institute (INEGA) – **Energy agency. EPC registration controller and regional register administrator.**

Regional Public Energy Agency of Castilla y León (EREN) – **Energy agency. EPC registration controller and regional register administrator.**

Centre for Energy, Environmental and Technological Research (CIEMAT) – **Energy research centre.**

Public Administration of Andalucía – **Public administration. Regulations on EPCs.**

Municipal Government of Alcorcon – **Municipality.**

Spanish Green Building Council – **Sustainable building Council of Spain.**

Certification Quality Control Laboratory of the Vasque Country – **Building quality control.**

Architects College of Madrid – **Architects association. EPC issuing and building construction/renovation.**

Ferrovial – **Highways, Airports, Construction and Energy Infrastructures Company.**

SACYR- **Infrastructures Company.**

Saint-Gobain-Isover – **Construction materials company.**

Tecnalia – **Technology reseach centre.**

CSIC – Institute of Eduardo Torroja - **Superior Council of Scientific Research. Building Energy division.**

Spanish Confederation of Consumer Cooperatives, Property Administrators and Resident Associations – **Consumer rights representative association.**

TECMARED – **Energy, Sustainability and New Technologies for Construction and Cities professional information Publisher.**

Main conclusions form discussions:

Identified weaknesses in national provisions for training for EPC issuers.

During the session of discussion directed by EREN, the following weaknesses have been identified:

- Competent technician definition.
- Lack of specific training in EPC issuers.
- Lack of robustness, derived from lack of training, producing a decrease of EPC quality.

Also, EREN presented as an example of the current situation the distribution of different professionals performing EPC assessments. The next graph shows that, even though there is vagueness of the definition of the capable professional for EPC issuing, most of the assessors are related with energy and construction sectors:

As it can be observed, 89,18% of the registered EPC assessors in Castilla y León region are Architects, Technical Architects, Industrial Engineers, and Technical Industrial Engineers. That situation leads to a 10,74% of non-qualified by direct academic background professionals. In this sense, although the current regulation on academic qualifying background has to be modified, the Spanish EPC market is operated by

construction-related technicians with solid backgrounds. The next table specifies the list of professionals performing EPCs:

Academic background	n	%
Architect	3.181	41,77%
Technical architect	2.194	28,81%
Industrial Engineer	857	11,25%
Technical Industrial Engineer	559	7,34%
Energy Engineer	9	0,12%
Mines Engineer	99	1,30%
Mechanic Engineer	16	0,21%
Roads, canals and ports Engineer	154	2,02%
Civil Engineer	59	0,77%
Agronomical Engineer	150	1,97%
Forestal Engineer	66	0,87%
Telecommunications Engineer	50	0,66%
Naval Engineer/architect	4	0,05%
Electricity Engineer	15	0,20%
Aerospace Engineer	15	0,20%
Topograph	50	0,66%
Chemical Engineer	8	0,11%
Ingeniero/a Técnico de Obras Públicas	104	1,37%
Geologist	1	0,01%
Physicist	3	0,04%
Others	15	0,20%
Total	7.609	

However, both last weaknesses are directly related to the training of the issuers. What have been shown during the period of time that EPCs have been carried out is that the problem might be related to EPC software use or building energy performance concepts deriving in lacks of robustness.

Potential improvements in national EPC training process

The QualDeEPC project, after the national workshop, proposes a regular and compulsory training for all EPC certifiers. They propose a longer first training cycle, in which the basics of handling and calculating the world of EPCs are taught. After that first stage, the training is followed by a regular shorter training sessions to refresh all the basic concepts.

Another alternative to regular compulsory training is QualDeEPC's second proposal for the improvement and harmonisation of advisor training. In this sense, they do not impose mandatory training, but they do impose a requirement to obtain accreditation to be able to issue EPCs.

Regarding either situation, whether training or a mandatory exam control, the training of professionals is organised around the following areas:

- Changes in national or European Building Performance Acts
- State-of-the-art technologies.
- Deep energy renovation recommendations.
- Common mistakes or errors in EPCs,

- Funding programs for renovation and their technical requirements,
- Consumer information and communication.
- Contract design.
- Further (soft) skills for EPC assessors.

The content presented as basic training for an energy efficiency certifying assessors is sufficient to ensure the quality of the expected service. We do not believe that any requirement should disappear. Thus, even if such training is provided, it is necessary to consider the different profiles of professionals who can work in this field. As already has been explained, the Spanish regulation allows professionals to issue EPCs if they have received formal training in engineering or architecture fields. We realise that both professionals need the other to carry out a completely controlled job. The engineer's profile usually has a vast knowledge of the technical systems, while they may lack the criteria on the interventions or behaviour of the envelopes. Whereas, and vice versa, the architecture/construction professionals are more experienced from their basic training in constructive solutions but do not control the systems as engineers do.

Would the training provided be sufficient to equalise the knowledge bases of these professionals or, on the contrary, in order to promote a wave of renovation, it is more coherent to ensure that EPCs are issued by an interdisciplinary team. This is a thought that we can leave open for the time being.

SECOND EVENT: Buildings Energy Efficiency Certification, Assessor Commission meeting.

DATE: 20 December 2022

PLACE: Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITERD), Madrid

Stakeholder organisations represented and their role in energy performance certification process:

General Energy Efficiency Sub-directorate, dependent of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITERD) – **Energy National Policies (amongst other things).**

State Secretariat for Energy, dependent of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITERD) – **Energy National Policies (amongst other things).**

Climate Change Spanish Office (OECC), dependent of Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITERD) – **Climate Change related Policies.**

Institute for Diversification and Energy Savings (IDAE), dependent of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITERD) – **Dissemination, technical training, and research on energy efficiency (amongst other things).**

Ministry for Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda (MITMA) – **Dwellings, Buildings and Urbanism Policies (amongst other things).**

Ministry for Consumption – **Protection and Defence of consumer's rights (amongst others).**

Ministry for Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda (MITMA) – **Dwellings, Buildings and Urbanism Policies (amongst other things).**

Autonomous Communities Governments (Andalucía, Aragón, Castilla La Mancha, Castilla y León, Cataluña, Islas Canarias, Comunidad de Madrid, Comunidad Foral de Navarra, Comunidad Valenciana, Extremadura, Galicia, La Rioja, Islas Baleares, País Vasco, Principado de Asturias, Murcia and Cantabria) – **Public administration. Regulations on EPCs.**

Other entities/organisations

Main conclusions form discussions:

Identified weaknesses in national provisions for training for EPC issuers.

In the section 6 of the meeting, the Committee discussed about the news on the competent technician definition amendment. Essentially the discussion focused on the commissionaires' doubts around the quality of EPCs and the training courses.

The general doubts about the training courses resided on the quality and adequacy for acquiring the needed knowledge and skills around EPC issuing.

The Ministry is currently working on the training courses contents to adjust them to the expectations.

Aside, some of the participants asked about the organisation to teach those courses. Eventually, those training procedures would be held as an open market, giving the regional governments competencies to quality control the organisations.

Potential improvements in national EPC training process

The round of discussion ended by expecting the future changes to be proposed by the Project of modifications of RD 390/2021. This modification of the current regulations firstly will try to clarify the quality EPC assessor needed background but also might implement a regular training methodology.